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**TESTING OBSERVERS OF PLANT COMPOSITIONAL DIVERSITY IN
FOREST MONITORING**

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ABSTRACT

This thesis deals with forest monitoring and with the assessment of the inter-observer error in vegetation survey. I participated in the life project “LIFE MODERn NEC” which is part of the National Emission Reduction Commitments Directive (NEC) and it’s focused on the monitoring and reduction of air pollutants. The main aims of the project were the enhancement of the ICP FORESTS PROGRAM for the forest ecosystem survey with the development of new indicators and study protocols.

Thesis work includes the ‘Quality Assurance Program’ for vegetation monitoring, which contributes to standardise the monitoring protocols for the warranty of data quality and comparability. I was involved within a series of activities: preliminary writing and elaboration of the official field manuals, training and intercalibration course for the surveyors, field check activity, MODERnNEC official monitoring campaign in 2023, and data analysis. The inter-observer error was assessed through the estimation of the data variability and the comparison among the means for each surveyor team for different variables. Furthermore, the variability of the “species richness” variable among five different training and intercalibration courses held in different years was assessed through the percentage coefficient of variation (CV%).

The analysis proved that the training of observers was effective in the reduction of the observer error for some variables bringing to a convergence of the surveyor’s estimations and to reduce the misunderstandings of the monitoring procedures after the training and intercalibration session.

Furthermore, the analysis of the CV% of the species richness year by year defined a decreasing trend of the observer estimations variability, suggesting that the improvement of the field manual together with the reiteration of training sessions are a winning combination in the reduction of the inter-observer error.

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Forest monitoring programs and the Life MODERnNEC project

Environmental and ecological monitoring has become particularly relevant in the last decades. Indeed, rising attention to the environmental issue has brought the public and the political institutions toward a greater sensibility and consciousness about the importance of environmental monitoring. Particularly, a present and proper matter of attention is the vegetation survey and evolution of the plant communities (Archaux et al., 2009, Chytry et al., 2011, Boch et al., 2022). For this aim, several projects worldwide have arisen. The most important one is likely the ONU-ECE **ICP Forests programs** (International Co-operative Programme on Assessment and Monitoring of Air Pollution Effects on Forests - with the Italian network named ‘CONECOFOR’), a long-term program launched in 1985 with monitoring windows every five years. The ICP Forest Program is organised into two networks: LEVEL I and LEVEL II network. The LEVEL I of the program was a more extensive network including 6000 monitoring sites all over Europe. On the other hand, the LEVEL II was less broad and included 800 monitoring sites. In addition, a new European directive 2016/2284, the **National Emission reduction Commitments directive** (NEC) arose, its aim is to set national air emissions reduction commitments for Member States and reduce their concentration monitoring and effects on the terrestrial and aquatic ecosystems. The main pollutants at issue are the nitrogen oxides (NO_x), non-methane volatile organic compounds (NMVOCs), sulphur dioxide (SO₂), ammonia (NH₃) and fine particulate matter (PM_{2.5}), and other secondary ones.

More recently, an important event was represented by the incorporation of some projects, in particular the ICP Forests Programs within the NEC Italy Network (National Decree of 26 November 2018) with a following large cooperation among “Comando unità forestali, ambientali e agroalimentari” (Command of forest, environmental and agribusiness unit - CUFAA), “Ministero dell'Ambiente e della Tutela del Territorio e del Mare” (Ministry of the environment and for the territory and sea tutelage - MATTM, currently MASE), “Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche” (Research National Council - CNR), “Consiglio per la ricerca in agricoltura e l’analisi dell’economia agraria” (Council for the agriculture research and the analysis of the agriculture economy - CREA).

Nevertheless, with the ongoing of time, it has been pointed out that despite the Italian monitoring network was well structured to represent the national condition of air pollution, it wasn’t sufficient to fully assess the degree of impact on the Italian ecosystems, mainly because it was missing:

- A complete representativeness of ecosystem types.
- An integration among sites managed by different organisations.

- An integration of results.

In fact, while a picture of air pollutants emissions is sufficiently structured at national level, the study of the air pollution impacts on ecosystems is still not truly representative of many Italian ecosystem types. The NEC network for Italy is built up today upon six forest sites, but it is possible that these ones couldn't be sufficiently representative of the Italian biogeographical and ecological complexity. From this principle, it arose the idea that the Italian NEC Network needed to be implemented and reformed to prove whether the current indicators used in the NEC network were suitable to depict the complexity of air pollution impacts on forests and freshwater ecosystems of the Mediterranean basin.

Hence, the LIFE MODERnNEC project, was developed with the general aim to test new indicators for the study of air pollution impact on terrestrial and freshwater ecosystems, particularly:

- To fulfil the needs of the National Emissions Ceilings (NEC) Directive (2016/2284/EU) on the establishment of national emissions ceilings of certain atmospheric pollutants, linking them to the impacts on ecosystems.
- To establish a network of monitoring sites that is fully representative of the Italian variety of freshwater and forest ecosystem types, by selecting additional representative forest and freshwater sites within the Mediterranean climatic region to cover broader ranges of sensitivity to acidification (based on Acid Neutralizing Capacity), pressure (pollution loads) and phytoclimates.
- To introduce and to test a new set of indicators and develop new monitoring protocols to study the impacts of air pollution on biodiversity (understory vascular plant functional groups and combinations, lichens, selected faunal taxa, selected biological indicators in water bodies) and air pollution chemistry and transparency.
- To allow the measurement of pollutant effects in remote areas, that may give the amplitude of background level for comparison with health-related impacts in urban areas.
- To assess mass balances of the major nutrients and pollutants flows through the atmosphere forest-soil water system, in order to quantify the long-term trends of the most relevant impacts.
- To discriminate between impacts resulting from pollutant emissions and from other drivers (climate change, management, land-use) by applying a multivariate statistical approach on NEC Directive target pollutants and the data collected during the 20-year activity of environmental monitoring at ICP Forests and ICP Waters sites in Italy.
- To improve the awareness-raising impact of the Italian and European NEC network by promoting Internet data dissemination through the FAIR

(Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Re-usable) Data Principle and the development of one specific software.

- To raise Italian public awareness about pollution sources and their impacts on ecosystems and promoting the NEC network.
- To increase knowledge exchanges between EU Member States involved in NEC implementation in order to discuss and promote common strategies and solutions.
- Enhancing the potential of NEC infrastructures may support governance and policies for human wellbeing and resilience towards sustainability in the context of the covid-19 crisis and the foreseen recovery and adaptation to post-pandemic scenarios. In this respect, the project will increase the capacity to monitor short-to-long term impacts of the pandemic and the response policy.

The project will improve quantitatively and qualitatively the NEC database to satisfy the needs and requirements of art. 9 of NEC Directive. The revised NEC Network comprises a total of **20 sites** (10 forest and 10 freshwater ecosystems, 4 additional terrestrial surveyed sites and 6 additional freshwater sites with respect to the previous NEC Network); thus, a higher number of locations are being monitored with a new set of indicators. The forest sites, inherent to the objectives of this thesis, are:

01ABR1 - Selva Piana (CH)
03CAL1 - Piano Limina (RC)
05EMI1 - Carrega (PR)
09LAZ1 - Monte Rufeno (VT)
12PIE1 - Val Sessera (BI)
*14SAR1 - Marganai (CI)
20VEN1 - Pian di Cansiglio (BL)
*25TOS2 - Cala Violina (GR)
*27BOL1 - Passo del Renon (BZ)
*31VEN2 - Bosco Fontana (MN)

The asterisks (*) indicate the 4 terrestrial sites added in the revised NEC network. These acronyms are divided in three parts and each indicates a different feature of the site. For instance, 01ABR1 can be splitted in:

- 01 - the chronological number of the site (between 01 and 32 in the LEVEL II Network).
- The 'alpha' code of three capital letters indicates the Italian administrative region (e.g., ABR = Abruzzo)
- 1 is the number of the site.

Life MODERnNEC project structure

LIFE MODERn NEC belongs to the LIFE Network and was structured into different actions and sub-actions:

A. PREPARATORY ACTIONS

A.1 Analysis and evaluation of existing data of atmospheric pollutant emissions, depositions and forest and freshwater responses in Italy. A multivariate approach was exploited to discriminate the impacts of air pollutants from those of other environmental factors (e.g. forest management or climate change).

A.2 Analysis and revision of current monitoring protocols to better respond to the requirements of the NEC Directive. Specific attention was focused on protocols concerning: 1. Ozone effects and pollutant fluxes in forest ecosystems; 2. Plant diversity; 3. Epiphytic lichens.

B. CORE ACTIONS

B.1 Selection of at least 4 forest and 6 freshwater additional monitoring sites for inclusion in the Italian NEC network. New sites provided data on the most representative forest types and aquatic sites in Italy, with varying levels of sensitivity to air pollutants and subject to deposition gradients. The main objective was to lead the Italian NEC network to the number of 10 forest and 10 freshwater sites, for a total of 20 monitoring sites.

B.2 Definition of a new set of indicators for the study of atmospheric pollution impacts on ecosystems. At Italian sites, biological monitoring has been limited until now and biological indicators needed to be tested and eventually adapted to ecosystem types. The project explored 4 additional biodiversity indicators macro-categories: 1. Macroinvertebrates and diatom assemblages in sensitive water bodies; 2. Plant functional and community-based assemblages in forest sites; 3. Priority and threatened epiphytic lichen species in forest sites; 4. Faunal diversity in forest sites. Further, monitoring protocols for air chemistry and transparency (i.e., visibility) have been introduced for testing within Action B.3.

B.3 Implementation and testing of existing and newly proposed indicators at existing and newly selected monitoring sites. Surveys were conducted on the above indicators, divided into three categories: biological response, ecosystem chemistry and meteorological data. This activity provided information about direct (e.g. nitrogen emissions) or indirect (e.g. climate change) air pollution stressors.

B.4 Training for field operators. Based on the technical protocols adapted within actions A.2 and B.2, training seminars for field operators in charge of site monitoring have been organised.

B.5 Establishing a permanent working panel composed by project partners and the Italian Ministry of the Environment (competent authority for the implementation of the NEC Directive) to promote the good compliance of the Italian NEC network with the requirements of Article 9. The working panel was set in the early stage of the project and has to periodically meet to assess the progress of actions B.1, B.2 and B.3. The working panel's main output are: updated Italian NEC network; Technical Guidelines based on the results of actions B.1 and B.2; Standards for a national database.

B.6 National awareness raising campaign addressing the general public and stakeholders on the need to adopt concrete measures to improve air quality. The campaign includes a national conference; local communication events; training seminars for teachers; and a National School Contest. Moreover, the air pollution chemistry and transparency monitoring station are used to involve the public during 2 dissemination events.

C. MONITORING THE PROJECT IMPACT

C.1 Monitoring of project impact and socio-economic effect. Assessment of the effectiveness of the improved NEC network to comply with the requirements of Article 9 of the NEC directive.

D. DISSEMINATION ACTIONS

D.1 Dissemination planning and execution. Design and production of a Communication Plan (visual identity / communication strategy), information materials, website, and social profiles, media relations activities, final international conference.

D.2 Networking and replicability. Promotion of the replicability of project's approach/methodology by presenting new monitoring indicators and sites in the context of the ICP Forests experts panel, the ICP WATERS and the NEC Working Group in charge of the revision of the NEC Directive in 2025 (technicians of project partners are part of both these groups). Networking with other LIFE and non-LIFE projects.

E. PROJECT MANAGEMENT AND THESIS TASKS

E.1, E.2, Overall project coordination, monitoring of project progress and key performance indicator (KPI).

I participated in some steps of the project that mainly concerned the preliminary A.2 action and the more advanced B.2 / B.3 / B.4 actions.

At the beginning, I took part in the revision activity of the already existing monitoring protocols (ACTION A.2) and to the development and elaboration of an updated manual with the new selected indicators to be employed and tested (ACTION B.2). This part of the thesis work was going for the early months until the official deadline that was fixed by April 2023.

Furthermore, I joined Dr. Marco Cervellini to build a team that would have performed the field activities.

Thus, the second step of my thesis work concerned the **training and intercalibration course** (T & I Course) held from June 5 to 8, 2023 at the Marsiliana Natural Reserve (ACTION B.4). The course was an important component of the Quality Assurance Program (QA), of which principal objectives were to provide the formation for the four involved surveyor teams and, as a consequence, to standardise the survey procedures and assure quality, replicability, and comparability of the collected data. The T & I course was structured into different phases, with an alternation of field activities where the indicators and observers were tested with the application of monitoring procedure and meetings to discuss the weaknesses and strengths of the manual and the results of the field training.

Subsequently, I participated in another step of the Quality Assurance Programme: the field check (ACTION B4). This check was performed on July 18th, 2023, at the site of Cala Violina (GR) concurrently with the official monitoring campaign of the MODERnNEC. During the control activity, the control team, composed by Dr. Marco Cervellini and me, controlled the work done from another surveyor team. The field check consisted of a “collaborative interaction” between the control and surveyor team and its main aim was to verify the correct application of the monitoring procedures for the assurance of quality standards. Moreover, the field check allowed us to assess whether the results of the T & I course were confirmed, and which could have been the causes of opposite outcomes. The field check also allowed to infer further possible lapses in the manual that didn't emerge at the course. Finally, I presented the results of the field check through an official report to the project coordinator, Prof. Roberto Canullo.

Later, I was directly involved in the official monitoring campaign of the MODERnNEC (ACTION C.1) which started in July 2023. My team went to Piano Limina (Reggio Calabria) and Selva Piana (Chieti) between the end of July and the beginning of August and performed the field survey in two beech forest sites. In this activity we applied the manual and monitored the vegetation in the two sites according to its directives and standards. The monitoring was a

cooperative activity, and the final data were a result of a shared point of view from the observers.

Finally, to conclude my thesis work, I evaluated the data of the training and intercalibration course in 2016 (only post-training) and in 2023 (both pre- and post- training) to assess for each team the **observer error** in terms of the surveyor visual estimate variation of vascular plant species richness and vertical vegetation layers cover.

In addition, I analysed the datasets derived from further training and intercalibration courses held in the previous years (2009, 2011, 2012, 2016) to assess the variability between different T & I courses, by computing the percentage coefficient of variation (CV% ($CV = \sigma / \mu * 100$)) for the “species richness” variable.

Error assessment and quality assurance program

The problem of error assessment in vegetation studies isn't a recent concern; indeed, it began to be central in the 40s of the 19th century. Untimely studies from Hope-Simpson, 1940 reported the drastic degree of influence of the error on vegetation monitoring (Morrison, 2016).

Sources of error may be multiple in long-term investigations (Kapfer et al., 2017). Particularly, there may occur severe issues of georeferentiation of plots (the “relocation error”, Boch et al., 2022), standardisation and harmonisation of data with very old data sets. In addition, it's especially arduous and wildcat to make comparisons between old and recent datasets although they were re-sampled at the same location and with the same survey procedure. Variability of the environment, of the disturbance magnitude and types, the observer turnover may lead to erroneous inferences about the data collected. Finally, it seems truly tough to assess the error caused by the ‘pseudoturnover’ of the observers when data were collected by other surveyors decades before which aren't able to witness and recount their past monitoring work anymore. Pseudoturnover consists in the inter-observer variation between the species detected within the same plot by different observers (Boch et al., 2022).

Hence, the point of assessment and quantification of error in vegetation survey is more relevant than ever, given the increasing awareness in the search for data reliability and quality (Li Cai et al., 2015). Implementation of already existing and creation of new datasets are fundamental actions for the improvement of the environmental and ecological research; nevertheless, it may be pointless, or even harmful, to get long series of data for which we can't have any certainty of their reliability and neither of their comparability with modern data.

Today, despite the strong technological development with the onset and progression of satellite imagery (Beck et al., 2006, Huylenbroeck et al., 2020)

and the use of drones (De Castro et al., 2021), the human observer still plays a central role. However, it's truly and widely proved that humans are prone to commit errors because of several factors and phenomena. For instance, variables such as the cover abundance of plants may undergo observer subjectivity and be directly affected by secondary factors such as the degree of experience and training, the emotional and tiredness state of surveyors, and other personal human aspects (Allegrini et al., 2009, Archaux et al., 2009, Morrison, 2016; Morrison & Young, 2016, Seidling et al., 2019, Morrison et al., 2020, Boch et al., 2022).

Particularly, Lloyd W. Morrison (2016) analysed 59 articles dealing with the quantitative estimation of the error in the vegetation monitoring field. He found that for the 92% of the studies considered, it was attested a statistically significant consequence of observer error on the vegetation surveys.

The aspect of observer error is particularly exacerbated with long-term monitoring programs where a severe and frequent turnover of observers may occur, and where the study area may undergo environmental and ecological variations in time. Thus, to avoid inaccurate or even erroneous inferences it has become particularly important to know the degree of reliability and the error magnitude of data, mostly in such kinds of programs such as the ICP Forests (Allegrini et al., 2009). Indeed, with ecological investigations and monitoring, there is a strong need for high-quality data: in other words, data should be reliable, comparable, and accessible. In the ICP Forests, for reaching this scope, a Quality Assurance (QA) Program was built. Error assessment is just a basic component of the QA and provides estimates of accuracy and precision (Allegrini et al., 2009). Accuracy refers to the closeness of an observation to the quantity intended to be observed; instead, precision is associated with a class of measurements and refers to the way repeated observation conform to themselves (in other words, it is related to the dispersion of observations or to a measure of it) (Stallings & Gillmore, 1971).

The QA protocol employed for the survey of vegetational components within the Italian monitoring program of forest systems (Ferretti et al., 2013) drives the entire process since the beginning steps (Allegrini et al., 2009).

Thus, the QA activities are milestones to verify the quality of the work done by the observers. Figure 1 illustrates the whole procedure of the QA from the beginning steps to the ultimate ones.

Fig. 1 QA/QC Flow Chart of the Vegetation Assessment in the CON-ECOFOR programme; from Canullo, modified.²⁵

Figure 1. Flow chart of the Quality Assurance Program (Allegrini et al., 2009).

Quality process is therefore composed of several phases:

- 1) Development of clear and intelligible manuals.
- 2) Selection of surveyors with adequate experience and formation.
- 3) Theoretical-practical course of training and intercalibration.
- 4) Final exercise and development of a common check list of expected species in the areas.
- 5) Field surveys by strictly following the manuals.
- 6) Performing field checks during the monitoring work to assess the work's quality of survey teams.
- 7) Computerization and transmission of data.
- 8) Cross checks through database, validations and data acquisition.
- 9) Transmission of all the documentation inherent to the project.
- 10) Final reporting and feedback.

Thus, the strict structure of the QA Program was established to minimise or, even, completely avoid errors of every kind. From those deriving from eventual misunderstandings of the monitoring procedures to the formation of the

surveyor personnel, to those related to the recording, computerization, and transmission of data.

Though, error may have a multiple nature. First, it is distinguishable between the intra- and inter observer. As reported by Morrison (2016), the intra-observer error occurs when the same surveyor or surveyor team get different results at different times, while the inter-observer error occurs when two or more observer or surveyor teams obtain different results at the same time. Furthermore, Morrison (2016) and Morrison et al. (2020) accurately describe that there are at least three common types of observer error during vegetation surveys:

Overlooking error (when species present are missed from the observer).

Misidentification error (when species are being erroneously identified).

Estimation error (when abundances aren't correctly assessed).

Yet, these three kinds of error contribute to the pseudoturnover which may be useful to estimate the overall observer error. This estimation, earliest introduced by Lynch & Johnson in 1974, may refer to the apparent changes in species composition caused by the human error during the observation. Nilsson & Nilsson's (1982, 1983, 1985) found a way to calculate this index and gave the chance for this to be later employed for the error quantification (Morrison et al., 2020).

Aims of the thesis

The aims of the analysis were:

- to assess the variability between the observers at the training and intercalibration courses (T & I course) within the Life MODERnNEC project between the pre- and post- training exercises in 2023 and between the post-training exercises in 2016 and 2023. Furthermore, to assess the variability occurred among five different ICP T & I courses (2009, 2011, 2012, 2016, 2023) for the attribution of the variable "species richness" (i.e. the number of species detected).

2.0 MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 STUDY AREAS

Area of the T & I course: Marsiliana Natural Reserve

The area where the training and calibration course was performed for the 2023 exercises (and for that in 2016 as well) was the Marsiliana Natural Reserve in the province of Grosseto (Figure 2). In a portion of the reserve’s forest four 10m x 10m SU were fixed in 2023. The forest site was a typical Mediterranean woodland with a dominance of species of *Fraxinus ornus* (Linnaeus) and *Fraxinus oxycarpa* (M.Bieb. ex Willd.) with further less abundant species such as *Phillyrea latifolia* (Linnaeus), *Quercus cerris* (Linnaeus) and *Quercus pubescens* (Willd).

Areas of the official monitoring campaign: Abruzzo and Calabria

In the study areas of Abruzzo (SITE: 01ABR1) and Calabria (SITE: 03CAL1) (Figure 2) during the official monitoring campaign of the MODERnNEC (ACTION C.1). These sites were characterized by tall, “adult” beech forests. In this situation, the species number found in all the vegetation layers was generally low, most of all in the sites of Abruzzo.

Indeed, in Abruzzo, the tree layer was exclusively dominated by *Fagus sylvatica* (Linnaeus) trees with a high coverage all over the study area. The shrub layer was scarce, and, in many SUs, it was completely absent. When the shrub layer was occurring, its cover was generally low, and it was exclusively composed of *Fagus sylvatica* shrubs.

Table 1 and table 2 illustrate the main biotic and abiotic characteristics of the two areas:

Site	Coordinates	Elevation	Slope (%)	Aspect	Bedrock and soil type	Bare soil and rocky outcrops (%)	Stand age (yrs)	Mean annual P (mm year ⁻¹)	Mean annual T (° C)	Summer P–PET ratio (June–July–August)
ABR1	+415051N+133523E	1500	30	SW	Limestone-Aluandic Andosol	1.8	125	1300	10	0.52
CAL1	+382538N+161047E	1100	20	NE	Granites–Haplic Umbrisol	2.5	125	1500	10	0.19

Table 1. The main abiotic features of the studied beech sites. Table from Campetella et al., 2020 but extrapolated from Fabbio et al., 2006; Hijmans et al., 2005; Trabucco & Zomer, 2009.

Site	Tree species	Tree species	Mean dbh (cm)	Site Basal area (m ²)	Mean height (m)	Top height (m)	Canopy depth (m)	LAI (m ² /m ²)	Leaf litter (Mg ha ⁻¹)
ABR1	899	1	23.7	40.09	19.50	24.60	9.30	4.67	2.969
CAL1	333	2	39.1	39.90	24.10	28.60	14.10	4.36	4.644

Table 2. The main stand structural features of the studied beech sites. Table from Campetella et al., 2020, but data from Fabbio et al., 2006.

Figure 2. Sites of activity: Marsiliana (T & I course), Selva Piana (Monitoring), Piano della Limina (Monitoring).

2.2 SAMPLING DESIGN AND VARIABLES OF INTEREST

The sampling design and variables of interest were those employed in the official 2023 MODERnNEC monitoring campaign in the selected sites of the LEVEL II ICP Network (Canullo et al., 2012).

Among the ten forest sites of LII two sites were selected (Abruzzo 01ABR1 and Calabria 03CAL1).

Nevertheless, before the beginning of the monitoring campaign, the variables to be detected, and the survey teams were all tested during the training and intercalibration course held at the Marsiliana Natural Reserve from June 5th to June 8th, 2023.

There were three types of sampling activities that were scheduled in the project and each of them had different variables of interest and aims:

- Survey within the 10 m x 10 m sampling units (SU).
- Survey with the JNP transect.
- Collection of samples for the SLA index calculation.

Survey within the 10 m x 10 m sampling units (SU)

The experimental design for the monitoring activity of plant biodiversity included observations within **10m x 10m quadrat SU** already installed over the study areas. For this activity, organisms of interest are the vascular, bryophytic and lichen species growing over the mineral soil. In each surveyed site, the SUs were distributed partly within a fixed metallic fence (of the LTER LEVEL II) and partly outside the fence. It was established to monitor 24 SUs for each site: 12 externals to the fence and 12 internal to the fence. As a rule, surveys would have begun starting from the external SUs and then with those located inside the fence. SUs were already marked and indicated on the field manual and the survey was performed on already sampled SUs during the ICP Forest program. So, a continuity in the data collection was provided with this new resampling in the MODERnNEC project.

As a rule, each survey team was composed of two observers. Thus, the results of the monitoring activity would have been a shared interpretation of the surveyors. To reduce as much as possible the footfall and the disturbance within the SU, only one observer would have worked inside the SU at a time.

Within each SU, different variables (table 3) were assessed by the surveyor teams: First, the **overall percentage cover**, and the **overall average height** of the whole vegetation layers were assessed. For overall percentage cover is intended the percentage of soil covered by the alive structure within the SU (trunks, leaver, branches, and seedlings), while for average height is intended the visually estimated average height for all the vegetation layers.

Further, the **foliage percentage cover** and the **average height** of each single vegetation layer (arboreal, shrub and herbaceous layer) were also estimated. In

addition, the percentage cover of the **litter layer** (organic litter of dead material such as leaves, branches, and dead trunks), **bare soil** (visible portions of mineral soil, including debris, rocks, and sediments) and **moss layer** (bryophytes and lichens growing on the mineral soil) were evaluated.

The discriminating parameters to classify the vegetation layers were the height and the morpho-physiology of the single species:

- **ARBOREAL LAYER - $h > 5 \text{ m}$** (Woody plants + lianas and climbing plants)
- **SHRUB LAYER - $0,5 < h \leq 5 \text{ m}$** (All woody plants + lianas and climbing plants)
- **HERBACEOUS LAYER - $h \leq 0,5 \text{ m}$** (All grasses and ferns and all woody plants)
- **MOSS LAYER** (All bryophytes and lichens on mineral soil, excluded those growing on woods, stones or other objects)

However, this classification has also some exceptions:

- Suckers of an individual plant falling in the tree layer may also belong to another layer if they result as independent. This was evaluated with the dominant and dominated structures criterion which is based on the evaluation whether the dominated structures would be independent by the dominant structure and, therefore, if the dominated structures would survive to the death of the dominant one.
- The coverage of plant trunks must be attributed to the vegetation layer they belong to and not to the layers they pass through.
- On the other hand, climbing plants (e.g. *vitis* sp) contribute with their cover to each layer they go through.
- Species such as *Ruscus aculeatus* (Linnaeus) or rhizomatous plants with herbaceous character, always belong to the herbaceous layer although they exceed the height of 0,5 metres.
- Litter includes the trunks of dead plants, but it doesn't include the trunk base of alive plants. So, litter is always lower than 100 %.
- Bryophytes and lichens growing over rock or decomposing wood can be considered only where a layer of humus is present over these latter.

A further, fundamental discriminating rule had to be respected: All the plants that were falling within the 10 m x 10 m SU perimeter were counted although they were rooted outside.

Second, it was performed the **identification and recording of the species** individuated and named by following the taxonomic identification of the flora d'Italia of Pignatti (1982) and it was attributed the **relative cover of each species**

in all the layers they go through within the SU. Relative cover of each species was attributed through the Braun-Blanquet scale which is made up of 7 values corresponding to a different percentage cover:

- r = rare
- + = $>0 <1\%$
- 1 = $\geq 1 <5\%$
- 2 = $\geq 5 <25\%$
- 3 = $\geq 25 <50\%$
- 4 = $\geq 50 <75\%$
- 5 = $\geq 75 \leq 100\%$

For instance, if inside a 10 m x 10 m SU a species is rare, with a cover lower than 0.5 square metres, the attributed value is r.

On the other hand, if a species is widely spread within a plot, with a surface overcoming 75 square metres, its value would be 5.

In the classifications of the plants, it was required at least the genus. Identification might even have been performed after the monitoring by taking pictures or collecting samples only outside the SU, to reduce the disturbance as much as possible. Finally, if an identification of the species was impossible to achieve, then the surveyor would just have taken a note on the note column in the field card.

As a rule, all the plants that were falling within the 10 m x 10 m SU perimeter were counted although they were rooted outside.

In the end, when the observers were monitoring the SU inner to the fence, they had to take a picture at the angle of the SU indicated by the graphical illustration at the annex 2 of the manual. This action was required to help the localization of the SU within the fence of the area.

The assessment of these variables was performed visually through the direct observation of the human eye. So, this kind of monitoring is clearly subjective to the observer perspective given by the degree of experience, the knowledge and comprehension circa the sampling procedure, and the physical and mental condition of the moment. Therefore, one of the interests would also be to assess how much the personal interpretation and perception of the surrounding field reality by means of the single surveyors can affect the outcomes of an investigation.

Figures 3 and 4 illustrate the arrangement of the plots respectively in the sites 01BR1 and 03CAL1.

01ABR1

In rosso il plot recintato con schema di rilevamento IN (in nero il sistema OUT)

03CAL1

AREA: 3 CAL 1

RILEVATORI: GANGALE - RASO

Figure 3 & 4. Schemes illustrating the arrangement of the sampling units respectively in the site of Abruzzo (01ABR1) and Calabria (03CAL1). The blue dots at the corner of the SUs showed up where the pictures had to be taken.

Variables of interest	12 SU inside the fence (IN) 12 SU outside the fence (OUT)
Overall percentage cover	IN & OUT
Average height of the tree layer	IN & OUT
Percentage cover of the tree layer	IN & OUT
Average height of the shrub layer	IN & OUT
Percentage cover of the shrub layer	IN & OUT
Average height of the herbaceous layer	IN & OUT
Percentage cover of the herbaceous layer	IN & OUT
Coverage of the moss layer	IN & OUT
Coverage of the litter	IN & OUT
Coverage of the bare soil	IN & OUT
Presence of vascular, moss or lichen species	IN & OUT
Vertical layer to which each species belongs (Code from 1 to 4)	IN & OUT
Species cover per layer (Braun-Blanquet rank)	IN & OUT
Photographic documentation	IN

Table 3. Table of the 13 Variables assessed in the MODERnNEC monitoring campaign within the 10 m x 10 m SU.

Survey with the JNP transect

The second monitoring activity performed was the so called JNP (Juhász Nagy pàl) transect consisting of a 100 metre long circular transect built up by 1000 square SU of 10 cm x 10 cm (figure 5, 6 & 7). This approach is based upon a dynasty of models conceived by Juhász Nagy-Pàl which are built on information theory. This survey relies upon the investigation at a fine scale of the real and potential combinations of species. Indeed, the JNP models can represent the ecological complexity in an easier and understandable way through a fine scale which is an integral part of the interpretation (Windi et al., 2004; Tsakalos et al., 2022).

Differently from the classical Shannon diversity index based on the number of species and their relative abundance, the variability of species combination is able to ponder a uneven distribution of the species and their relative preference for the local environmental (biotic-abiotic) conditions (Tsakalos et al., 2022).

So, inside each 10 cm x 10 cm SU, specific objects of interest were detected: the plant species growing on the mineral soil and the presence of other characteristic elements.

Some important discriminating rules had to be respected during the JNP transect survey (figure 8):

- Only the living structures that didn't exceed the height of 1.3 metres were considered.
- All the plants falling within the 10 cm x 10 cm SU perimeter were counted although they were rooted outside.
- Species taxonomy was based on the Flora d'Italia of Pignatti (1982) and the classification should have been assigned at least to the genus level followed by the acronym sp. (e.g. *Quercus sp.*). If the identification of the genus was impossible, then it was required to note down the presence of the unrecognised plant in the note space of the field sheets.
- It was forbidden to collect samples of plants within the SU to reduce the human impact inside the study area and to avoid alterations with its development.

Further objects of observations were detected whether they covered at least 50% of the SU surface. These elements were indicated via specific codes:

- W – Bryophytes, group (soil-dwelling mosses and liverworts).
- Y – Lichens, group (land-dwelling of any type).
- L – litter (set of leaves, fruits, fine debris, etc.).
- R – branches and dead wood on the ground.
- B – holes, burrows, animal ploughings.
- N – bare soil (including rocks, stones, surface roots, etc.).
- A – overlying shrubs ($\geq 1.30\text{m}$).
- X – other (specify with annotations).

A crucial step of this activity was the installation of the JNP transect which main aim was to collect and cross the various heterogeneity of the study area and, therefore, to pass through the different aspects of the understory such as different plant associations, topographic discontinuities, and clearings.

Thus, the shape of the transects should have had a tendency toward a circular shape, but it wasn't demanded to be a "perfect" circle.

It was required to place the transect far at least 40 cm from the base of tree trunks, isolated rocks and exceptional discontinuities which are not proper of the area.

Figure 5. Hypothetical arrangement of a JNP transect.

Figure 6. Practical example of a JNP transect disposition. The metric string crosses the main aspects of heterogeneity in the survey site (National Park of Foreste Casentinesi, 2022).

Figure 7. materialisation of the JNP transect (Marsiliana natural reserve, 2016)

Figure 8. The parallelepiped (10cmx10cmx130cm) defines the detection volume of functional parts of plants, includes the portions that come from outside and excludes those that exercise the function externally.

Collection of samples for the SLA index calculation

Functional traits (morphological, physiological and phenological) of plants are related to their shape and effect on the ecosystem processes. They can be indicative of ecological strategies and predictive of relationships with environmental components and processes, including alterations of biogeochemical phenomena (Perez-Harguindeguy et al., 2016).

Plant functional traits are considered valid and reliable indicators for monitoring ecosystem dynamics and answers of plant communities to the environmental variations (Standish et al., 2014; Brudvig 2017).

One of the most diffused traits used in ecology is the Specific Leaf Area (SLA) which is the ratio between the surface of a leaf and its dry mass. It is related to the concentration of leaf nitrogen (Perez-Harguindeguy et al., 2016), relatively simple to be computed and informative of the functionalities related to the leaf economy (i.e. photosynthetic efficiency, exploitation of nutrients and water, longevity of leaf structures).

Low values of SLA indicate reduced growth rates and conservative strategies of resource usage while high values of SLA are associated with faster growth rates and a strategy based on a higher exploitation of available resources.

In the MODERnNEC, for the determination of the SLA index, they were objects of observation of the main dominant plant species in terms of relative cover, only in the herbaceous layer within the already surveyed twelve 10 x 10 m SU inner to the fence.

In detail, it was required to select the well-developed and healthier leaves of the five most abundant species common to at least 2 SUs. Only one leaf per plant individual was collected and only five individuals per species were sampled. So, five leaves were collected for each species and in total 25 leaves were gathered for the five species of interest. Collected leaves had to be completely expanded, equipped with the petiole and possibly healthy and not affected by parasites or herbivores.

Selection of the most abundant species to be sampled was based on the mean of coverage values already attributed with the Braun-Blanquet scale during the monitoring inside the 10 m x 10 m SUs.

But, for the single values of the Braun-Blanquet rank, the median was considered. Thus, the computing of the mean coverage per species was performed by summing the median for each attributed code and then dividing for the number of times that species was detected in the 12 SUs.

Median values for each score of the Braun-Blanquet rank is as follow (Canullo et al., 2020):

- R = 0,01
- + = 0,5
- 1 = 3,0
- 2 = 15,0
- 3 = 37,5
- 4 = 62,5
- 5 = 87,5

Finally, they were acquired 2 parameters for the computation of SLA:

- 1) **Unilateral leaf surface** of a fresh leaf through the scanner of the leaves collection.
- 2) **Dry mass** once weight was stabilised (after drying out in the stove).

The extraction of the unilateral leaf area was performed with a scanning procedure. This implied that it could take a few hours before the scanning. During this time span, leaves could have dried out and deteriorated. Thus, it was needed to store leaves within humidified blotting paper, inside a plastic bag and then inside a thermal bag. Thus, the leaves would retain their properties until the process of scanning.

Scanning was divided in different steps:

- Leaves had first to be removed from the adsorbing paper and well-dried.
- A transparent plastic sheet had to be placed on the scanner plane, one leaf at a time layed above it, and a second plastic sheet had to cover the leaf. If the leaf was too large for the scanner plane (e.g. Carex sp leaves), it was

possible to break up the leaf and to scan the leaf parts together after splitting.

- Scanning at 300 dpi was performed and the file saved in bitmap format in black and white.
- File name was a code composed by the number of the SU, the species, and the leaf number. For instance, ABR1_Hedera helix_03; where ABR1 is Abruzzo and SU number 1, Hedera helix is the species and leaf number 3.
- After the scanning, each leaf was placed inside a paper envelope, the envelope was sealed, and the corresponding code was written on the outer side for the sample identification.
- In the end, the files with the scanned leaves were sent to the Unicom staff by email, while the physical leaf samples were sent through courier.

2.3 EXECUTION OF THE TRAINING AND INTERCALIBRATION COURSE

During the training and intercalibration course (Action B.4) at the Marsiliana natural reserve (June 5th-8th 2023), the survey teams that would have performed the official monitoring campaign were trained for two of the three different kinds of monitoring procedures: the 10 m x 10 m SU and the JNP transect; furthermore, the protocol was illustrated to them to collect, store and transmit the leaf samples for the SLA index. There were 4 teams at the T & I course in 2023 (team 32, 33, 34, 35). Each team was composed of two observers (among which Dr. Cervellini and me) with variable degrees of field experience and formation.

The T & I course was scheduled into different phases:

Day 1) June 5th - It was to await the arrival of all the people involved in the formation course (figure 9) to the carabinieri forestali station of Follonica (Gr) . Furthermore, the Unicom staff composed of three ecologists went to the field where the training would have been held and there, they placed the SUs (figure 10) for the survey exercise and checked the species present to produce a first check list.

Day 2) June 6th – A first meeting was done in the morning with the presentation of the personnel involved, the scopes and generalities of the MODERnNEC and of the T & I course specifically. After that, the teams moved to the field where the SUs were previously fixed by the Unicom staff. There were 5 SUs: 4 for the official training and the other one for a preliminary illustration and intercalibration. Thus, the surveyors had an initial shared moment for solving doubts and taking confidence with the local flora. After that, the teams started with the survey exertion within the 10 m x 10 m SU (**pre-training exercise**). Each team monitored a SU at a time and worked in shifts. The survey of the 10 m x 10 m SUs wasn't finished on the 6th, but just on the next day. Successively,

at the return to the carabinieri forestali station (figure 11), surveyors started with the data computerization and submission procedure.

Day 3) June 7th – In the morning, teams moved to the field and started again the exercise to complete the four quadrat SUs. After the end of this practice, the Unicom staff showed the procedure for the leaf sample harvesting for the SLA index. It was illustrated how to select the plants to be collected, how to collect the leaves, how to store the leaves until the scanning and finally, it was explained how to scan and transmit the files and the physical samples. After that, surveyors came back to the carabinieri station and in the afternoon, the completion of data computerization and transmission was done. With the submitted data, Dr. James Tsakalos, a researcher of the Unicom staff at that time, performed a preliminary analysis of the pre-intercalibration exercise to assess the distance between the teams for the variables: **species richness, overall coverage, relative coverage of tree, shrub, and herbaceous layers**. So, at this point, in the evening a new meeting was held to show up the outcomes of the preliminary analysis. Results didn't show an appreciable distance for the species richness variable. The most interesting outcome was related to the herbaceous and shrub layer with an overestimate of the shrub layer by means of 3 over 4 teams. The explanation of such data behaviour was related to the erroneous inclusion of the *Ruscus aculeatus* (Linnaeus) into the shrub layer. Indeed, as explained in the manual, *Ruscus aculeatus* (Linnaeus) always belonged to the herbaceous layer although it was exceeding the height of 0.5 metres. This error was corrected in that section. Other incongruencies with the manual were solved with the meeting which consisted in the intercalibration section where the different surveyors could have confronted each other and with the Unicom staff.

Day 4) June 8th – In the morning, the survey of the four SUs to collect data was repeated (**post-training exercise**) and the distance of each team in the post-intercalibration exercise assessed, with respect to the pre-intercalibration session. Once this first activity was finished, it was illustrated by the Unicom staff the procedure to lay down the JNP transect on the ground and how to perform the survey within the 10 cm x 10 cm SUs. Each team monitored a quarter of the transect (thus 25 metres) as an exercise to take confidence with the procedure. Once the field activities were over, the surveyors moved away from the training site to get back home and in the following days they performed the computerization and submission of the data.

I then worked on these data to assess the distance between the teams between the pre- and post-training exertions and to find the possible causes of the field outcomes that will be illustrated in the chapter of the 3.0 “result”.

Figure 9. Observer and unicom staff participating at the training and intercalibration course in Marsiliana.

Figure 10. Materialised plots at the training and intercalibration course at the Marsiliana Natural Reserve.

Figure 11. Guesthouse of the carabinieri forestali station of Follonica.

2.4 EXECUTION OF THE OFFICIAL MONITORING CAMPAIGN

The official monitoring Campaign of the MODERnNEC (Action C.1) started in the beginning of July 2023 and the previously trained teams began the survey of the 10 selected sites. I participated in the monitoring of the sites in Abruzzo and Calabria together with Dr. Marco Cervellini of the Unicom technical personnel. We left on July 27th, 2023, from Civitanova Marche (MC) to the study area in Piano Limina (RC) (site: 03CAL1). We monitored 03CAL1 area in 2 days, between July 28th and 29th. During the first day we surveyed all the SUs outside the fence and some of the inner ones (figures 12, 13 & 14), while on the second day we completed the monitoring of the SUs internal to the fence, performed the survey with the JNP transect and then collected the leaf samples for the SLA index determination (figure 15).

During the survey we have been particularly accurate in the limitation of the footfall over the SU to reduce as much as possible the harm and the impact on the local flora.

Successively, on the morning of July 30th, we left Calabria and moved toward Abruzzo. We started the monitoring of the Selva Piana area (CH) (site: 01ABR1) on July 31st, 2023. Surprisingly, we concluded all the field activities on the same day. Indeed, the condition of the area presented a scarce number of species and a low stratification of the understory vegetation layers. We finished the survey of the 10 m x 10 m SUs in the early afternoon (figure 16, 17 & 18), then performing the JNP transect (figure 19 & 20) was quick because of a large coverage of litter and scarcity of herbaceous species to be detected. Finally, we collected the samples for the SLA index computing. On the next day, August 1st, 2023, we left Abruzzo and came back to Camerino to deposit the samples and sort the field sheets.

In the further days, as indicated by the Quality Assurance protocol, Dr. Cervellini and me made the scanning of the field sheets with recorded data, brought them to the computer format rewriting them in the already established excel sheets and finally uploaded and submitted the data and the original scanned field sheets on the Ground Vegetation Portal.

In addition, the QA presumed the compilation of a final module (“activity report sheet”) at the end of field activity. This document contained questions helpful for a better and correct interpretation of the data and to assess the conditions of the work and of the surveyed area. It was asked for eventual problems of integrity of the LEVEL II fence, issues of logistic character and disposability from the personnel managing the sites. The module also asked for eventual provisional acronyms and definitions given to the species on the field.

Figure 12. Fence of the LEVEL II Network including the SUSs and other monitoring systems for the study of the environmental parameters and insects within the site 03CAL1 (Calabria). Dr. Marco Cervellini in the picture.

Figure 13. Situation internal to the fence with systems to monitor insects and the wood stakes that delineate the 10 m x 10 m SUs in 03CAL1.

Figure 14. The view of the survey site 03CAL1 from an overhead position.

Figure 15. Process of scanning of the leaf samples collected and exploited for the calculation of the SLA index. In this example, the samples collected were of the species *Rubus hirtus* in Calabria.

Figure 16. Fence of the LEVEL II Network in the site 01ABR1 (Abruzzo). Close the fence, the stakes delimiting the external 10 m x 10 m SUs.

Figure 17. Stakes delineating the SUs to survey in Abruzzo.

Figure 18. Fence including the internal SUs and other systems for the monitoring activity and the stakes delineating the external SUs in Abruzzo.

Figure 19. Materialised JNP transect in Abruzzo.
Dr. Marco Cervellini in the picture.

Figure 20. Metric band utilised for the JNP transect survey.

2.5 EXECUTION OF THE FIELD CHECK

The field check (Actions B.3 & B.4) was a collaborative control and represented an integral part of the Quality Assurance Program. Its main aim was to evaluate whether the survey teamwork was in accordance with the fixed standards and, therefore, whether data confirmed a high-quality level. The field check was performed by my team (control team) composed by Dr. Marco Cervellini and me (from now on team S-C) of the Unicam technical personnel at the site of Cala Violina (GR) (site: 25TOS2) on July 18th, 2023. The controlled team was composed of further two observers (from now on team L-M). Thus, both teams, (control and controlled) participated in the T & I course in 2023.

The team L-M was checked for 9 variables of interest established in the MODERnNEC project: overall percentage cover of all the vegetation layers, the coverage for the different vegetation layers (tree, shrub and herbaceous) plus the one of the litter and bare soil; finally, the number of total species detected and the number of those in each single vegetation layer in the SU were also assessed. The check activity consisted of a re-survey from the control team S-C on two already monitored SUs by the survey team L-M: one randomly selected SU within the fenced plots and one randomly selected SU outer to the fence. Random selection was done via an automatic generator of numbers on the phone. In the end, once the control team S-C completed the re-survey activity, a comparison was performed for the values found by the two teams and the results of the field check were also compared with the outcomes of the post-training exercise at the T & I course. Check field and the final confrontation was useful for different purposes: evaluate the level of understanding of the manual by mean of the observers, assess whether the training and intercalibration course properly worked for the surveyor formation and evaluate whether the data collected by the survey team are reliable and comparable with the other data collected by different survey teams.

The field check provided interesting perspectives that underlined strengths and weaknesses of the training and intercalibration course as well as of the check field itself. These considerations will be illustrated in chapters 3.0 “Results” and 4.0 “Conclusions”.

2.6 COMPLETION AND TRANSMISSION OF DATA

After the field work, for the completion of data, it was required the compilation of already prepared excel sheets for each activity. After the computerization of data, these had to be transferred together with the other documentation reported in chapters 1, 2, 3 of the field manuals.

Specifically, it was first required to scan the field sheet of activities: 10 m x 10 m SU plus the JNP transect together with the activity report sheet.

These files had specific coding names:

- **SS2023NNABCNCOPL** = scan sheets of inner SU + outer SU
- **SS2023NNABCNCOPS** = scan sheets of transect SU + activity report sheet

Where:

SS = Survey Sheet; 2023 = Survey year; NNABCN = Name of the plot; COPL/COPS = Data types.

While the excel sheet with the computerised data of the 10m x 10m SU survey had to be named with other coding:

- **23CopLnn** which indicated the data of total cover and of single vegetation layer cover.
- **23CopSnn** which indicated the data of detected species and relative cover per species (Braun-Blanquet ranking).
- **23SpAggnn** which indicated further species found only outside the monitored plots but not inside.

Where: 23 = 2023; CopL = Cover of layers; CopS = Cover of species; SpAgg = Additional species; nn = number of monitored plot.

Furthermore, for the data of the JNP transect survey, the excel sheets needed other coding:

23JNPSnn – Where 23 = 2023; JNPS = Species of JNP; nn= number of SU.

Once the various documents were named with the nomenclature illustrated in the manual, it was time for the transmission of data. This step was mediated through the *ground vegetation online portal*. Thus, each surveyor team with the support of the Unicam staff submitted the PDF and excel files with respectively the field sheets and the collected data. Ground vegetation is provided with tools to check the data stored in the excel sheets and to allow the operator to quickly individuate and rectify the errors. The tool employed in the MODERnNEC was “Controlla specie” (“Check species”) and allowed to control the names attributed to the species and to verify mistakes at taxonomic level. This avoided errors that may have caused, for instance, the finding of a higher species richness during the statistical analysis. Thus, in case of errors, the ground vegetation portal could have reported back to the operator the mistake and they could have rectified it. This almost nullifies the chance of error transmission and enhances the quality of the data themselves.

2.7 DATASET FROM PREVIOUS TRAINING AND INTERCALIBRATION COURSES (2009, 2011, 2012, 2016, 2023)

The datasets employed for the computing of the CV% are derived from previous training and intercalibration courses performed in the previous years at different locations and periods. In particular, the T & I course in 2009 was an international exercise performed at the Cansiglio site (BL) for the project FutMon carried out by 11 surveyor teams, each composed of a single observer from 11 different European countries.

On the other hand, in both the T & I courses in 2011 and 2012, there were 8 teams, each composed of two Italian surveyors. The activity was held at the Reserve of Abbadia di Fiastra (MC).

Finally, the T & I courses in 2016 and 2023 were both performed at the Marsiliana Natural Reserve (GR) respectively by three and four teams, each composed of two Italian observers. Thus, in 2016 were involved six surveyors, while in 2023 eight surveyors.

2.8 STATISTICAL ANALYSIS

Statistical analysis was performed to assess the variation between observers at the training and intercalibration course in 2016 (only post-training) and 2023 (both pre- and post-training) for the parameters “number of detected species” (or “species richness”), “overall percentage cover” and the “percentage cover of the tree, shrub, herbaceous and litter layers” within the 10 m x 10 m SUs.

I generated box plots using the “ggplot” package (Hadley Wickham, 2011) for the visual assessment of the estimate’s variability. I wanted to graphically illustrate the range of variable’s estimations between surveyor teams and within SUs; thus, the boxplots could provide fast and intuitive inferences about the data dispersion and about the median values.

A clarification has to be done, in the illustration of the results through the boxplots, I refer to the range, but this term refers to the interquartile range: the difference between the 75th percentile and the 25th percentile.

Furthermore, the statistically significant differences between the means of observations were assessed.

Initially, the Shapiro test was performed to assess the normality of the data. Nevertheless, the Shapiro test did often fail in the assessment of data normality. Moreover, since there was a reduced number of observations, the Shapiro test wasn’t completely reliable in the assumption of the data normality (Siebert & Siebert, 2017). Thus, the non-parametric Wilcoxon-Mann-Whitney test was performed to assess whether the means of observations differ significantly

between the pre- and post-training in 2023. I added the p-values in the box plot through the “stat_compare_means()” function from the package “ggpubr” (Kassambara, 2019).

Furthermore, the Kruskal-Wallis test was performed to infer whether a statistically significant difference in the means occurred between the estimates of the analysed parameters (among the teams and among the plots) for the single pre-training 2023, post- training 2023 and post-training 2016. Consequently, when the Kruskal-Wallis attested the significant difference among the observations, I also performed the Pairwise Wilcoxon Rank Sum Tests to assess among which couples there was a statistically significant difference of the mean values.

In addition, I calculated the percentage coefficient of variation (CV%) for each T & I course in 2009, 2011, 2012, 2016, 2023 for the “species richness” variable and generated a graph to illustrate whether a variation occurred year by year.

The coefficient of variation measures the variability of a series of numbers independently of the unit of measurement used for these numbers. To do so, the coefficient of variation eliminates the unit of measurement of the standard deviation of a series of numbers by dividing it by the mean of these numbers (Herve Abdi, 2010). So, CV is the ratio between the standard deviation σ and the mean μ :

$$CV = \sigma / \mu$$

Data processing and data visualisation was performed with R version 4.3.2 (R Core Team, 2020), using the following packages: base R coding (R Core Team, 2020), ggplot (Hadley Wickham, 2011), dplyr (Wickham et al., 2019), Tidyverse (Hadley Wickham, 2019), “ggpubr” (Kassambara, 2019), , vegan (Oksanen et al., 2008).

3.0 RESULTS

In this chapter, I first illustrated the field manual produced during the preliminary steps of my work. After, the results of the statistical investigation are illustrated. These results concern 6 of the 13 investigated variables within the 10m x 10m plots (see table 3, page 19): Species richness, overall coverage, tree, shrub, and herbaceous layer coverage and the litter coverage. I considered these variables because they could have presented the greatest critical points during the survey procedure. Furthermore, these variables were the most abundant within the SUs; For instance, there was no point in assessing variables such as the moss layer cover or the bare soil cover because they were almost irrelevant.

Structure of the results follow a systematic order: it's first shown a comparison of the boxplots with the relative p-values for the pre- and post-training exercises in 2023 and then it is illustrated the single pre-training 2023, post-training 2023 and then the post-training 2016 with the results of the Kruskal-Wallis test.

3.1 FIELD MANUAL

Revision of already existing manuals and the development of a new manual (figure 21) for the MODERn NEC with the development of new indicators for the vegetation survey (ACTIONS A.2, B.2 & B.3) was concluded before April 2023. The manual was structured into different sections:

- In the introduction, it preliminarily indicated the generalities of the project such as the forest monitoring sites, period of survey activity and aims of the survey and further instructions.
- Then, the first chapter illustrated the experimental design of the first survey activity that would have been performed within the 10 m x 10 m sampling units (from now sampling unit = SU), variables of investigations (plant species richness, vegetation layer height and cover), detailed indications for the attributions of the vegetation and species cover and further general instructions such as those for the reduction the human impact over the SU.
- Then, the second chapter explained the sampling scheme for the second survey activity: The detection of the plant species combinations (florula diversity) via a circular transect (also known as JNP transect by Juhász-Nagy Pál (1935-1993)) of 10 cm x 10 cm SUs.

At the end of each of these two chapters, examples of sheets for the data recording were illustrated.

- In the third chapter, the sample collection procedure for the determination of the Specific Leaf Area (SLA) index was illustrated.
- In the fourth chapter, the quality process (QA Program) of the whole monitoring process was shown and synthesised through a flow diagram.
- The fifth chapter displayed the procedure to complete and to computerise data, but even to transmit these to the project database for their storing and the statistical analysis. References and literature were also indicated at the end of the fifth chapter.
- In the last section of the manual, there are the last four attachments dealing with taking pictures from the understory 10 m x 10 m SU (Attachment 1), the maps illustrating the position of the 10 m x 10 m SU in the ICP forests monitoring sites (Attachment 2) and further recommendations.

LIFE MODERN(NEC)
Azione B3

Rilevamenti della vegetazione e della diversità vegetale

Rete NEC Italia - Indicatori di biodiversità forestale

Addestramento e intercalibrazione, Riserva Naturale Statale "Marsiliana" (GT): 5-8 giugno 2023

MANUALE DI CAMPO *Rilevamenti 2023*

Coordinamento

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Plant Data - Centro interuniversitario di ricerca per la Biodiversità vegetale e Big data
(Alma Mater Studiorum Università di Bologna)

Camerino 03/07/2023 (v1.3)

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Figure 21. Manual cover written in Italian for the MODERN(NEC) monitoring activity on Italian forest sites

3.2 SPECIES RICHNESS

Species richness among plots (SU)

Looking at the differences in species richness, recorded by the four teams in each plot (SU) for the pre- and post- training exercises in 2023 (figure 22), it was detected that:

- Inside the PLOT_1 a decrease of the range of the team estimates occurred in the post-training together with a slight increase in the median value.
- In the PLOT 2 an appreciable increase of the range between the estimates occurred in the post-training together with a slight decrease in the median value.
- Inside the PLOT 3 a considerable rise in the range of the estimates in the happened post-training together with a detectable increase in the median value.
- In the PLOT 4 there wasn't an appreciable variation of the range of the estimates between the pre- and post-training, but an increase in the median value occurred.

Nevertheless, the Wilcoxon test didn't attest statistically significant differences between the means of the observations before and after the intercalibration.

In the end, three outliers appear: in PLOT_3 and PLOT_4 for the pre-training and one in PLOT_1 for the post-training. These outliers exceed the interquartile range (IQR) of 1.5 times and therefore, they exceed the upper and lower whisker of the boxplot. In this case, these data are plotted outside the box plot and get the name of "outlying points" or "outliers".

Figure 22. Species richness for each plot (median is represented by the black cross line), calculated among the four teams between pre- and post-training exercises (2023). The pre-training interquartile range coloured in orange and the post-training coloured in green.

Considering the single pre-training exercise in 2023 (Figure 23 & 24), the non-parametric Kruskal-Wallis test attested that there is no statistically significant difference between the plots.

Figure 23. Species richness for each plot (median is represented by the black cross line), calculated among the four plots in the pre-training exercises (2023).

Kruskal-Wallis rank sum test

```
data: spp_richness by plot
Kruskal-wallis chi-squared = 7.6347, df = 3, p-value = 0.0542
```

Figure 24. Kruskal Wallis test for the pre-training exercise (2023) for each plot.

Considering the single post-training exercise in 2023 (Figure 25 & 26), the non-parametric Kruskal-Wallis test attested that there is a statistically significant difference in the means between the plots. The Pairwise Wilcoxon Rank Sum Test found this difference between the PLOT_1 / PLOT_3, PLOT_2 / PLOT_3 and PLOT_3 / PLOT_4.

Figure 25. Species richness for each plot (median is represented by the black cross line), calculated among the four plots in the post-training exercises (2023).

```

Kruskal-Wallis rank sum test

data: spp_richness by plot
Kruskal-Wallis chi-squared = 9.2775, df = 3, p-value = 0.02582
Pairwise comparisons using wilcoxon rank sum test with continuity correction

data: Dataset_spp_richness_post_2023$spp_richness and Dataset_spp_richness_post_202
3$plot

      plot_1 plot_2 plot_3
plot_2 0.460  -      -
plot_3 0.028  0.029  -
plot_4 1.000  0.384  0.029

P value adjustment method: none

```

Figure 26. Kruskal wallis and Pairwise Wilcoxon Rank Sum Test for the post-training exercise (2023) for each plot.

Considering the T & I course in 2016 (figure 27 & 28), the non-parametric Kruskal-Wallis test attested that there isn't a statistically significant difference between the means of species richness for the three plots.

Figure 27. Species richness for each plot (median is represented by the black cross line), calculated among the three plots in the post-training exercises (2016).

Kruskal-wallis ranksum test

```
data: spp_richness and plot
Kruskal-wallis chi-squared = 5.4678, df = 2, p-value = 0.06
```

Figure 28. Kruskal Wallis test for the post-training exercise (2016) for each plot.

Species richness between teams

Looking at the differences in species richness, recorded by the four teams for the pre- and post- training exercises in 2023, it was detected that (figure 29):

- TEAM_32 displayed a considerable increase in the range of team estimates in the post-training and the median value has slightly increased.
- TEAM_33 attested a slight decrease in the range of the estimates in the post-training, but an appreciable decrease in the median value occurred.
- TEAM_34 didn't show a perceptible increase in the range of the estimates in the post-training, but a substantial increase in the median value occurred.
- TEAM_35 demonstrated an appreciable increase in the range of the estimates in the post-training and a detectable increase in the median value occurred as well.

However, the Wilcoxon test didn't confirm statistically significant differences between the means of the observations before and after the intercalibration.

In the end, five outliers appear far from the boxes. These outliers are above the TEAM_34, 35 in the pre-training and above the TEAM_33, 34 and 35 in the post-training. These data exceed the IQR of 1.5 times and were plotted individually.

Figure 29. Species richness for each team (median is represented by the black cross line), calculated among the four teams between pre- and post-training exercises (2023). The pre-training interquartile range coloured in orange and the post-training coloured in green.

Considering the single pre-training exercise in 2023 (figure 30 & 31), the non-parametric Kruskal-Wallis test attested that there is no statistically significant difference between the surveyor teams for the species richness variable.

Figure 30. Species richness for each team (median is represented by the black cross line), calculated among the four teams in the pre-training exercises (2023).

Kruskal-Wallis rank sum test

```
data: spp_richness by team  
kruskal-wallis chi-squared = 5.1871, df = 3, p-value = 0.1586
```

Figure 31. Kruskal-Wallis for the pre-training exercise (2023) for each team.

Considering the single post-training exercise in 2023 (figure 32 & 33), the non-parametric Kruskal-Wallis test attested that there is no statistically significant difference between the surveyor teams for the species richness variable.

Figure 32. Species richness for each team (median is represented by the black cross line), calculated among the four teams in the post-training exercises (2023).

Kruskal-wallis rank sum test

```
data: spp_richness by team
Kruskal-wallis chi-squared = 2.9588, df = 3, p-value = 0.398
```

Figure 33. Kruskal wallis test for the post-training exercise (2023) for each team.

Considering the course in 2016 (figure 34 & 35), the non-parametric Kruskal-Wallis test attested that there is no statistically significant difference between the surveyor teams for the species richness variable.

Figure 34. Species richness for each team (median is represented by the black cross line), calculated among the three teams in the post-training exercises (2016).

Kruskal-wallis rank sum test

```
data: spp_richness by team
Kruskal-wallis chi-squared = 1.098, df = 2, p-value = 0.5775
```

Figure 35. Kruskal Wallis for the post-training exercise (2016) for each team.

3.3 OVERALL PERCENTAGE COVER

Overall percentage cover between plots

Looking at the differences in the overall percentage cover, recorded by the four teams for each plot for the pre- and post- training exercises in 2023, it was detected that (figure 36):

- Inside the PLOT_1 a drastic decrease in the range of the team estimates occurred in the post-training and the median value has considerably arisen.
- In the PLOT 2 a considerable decrease in the distance between the estimates occurred in the post-training and an appreciable increase in the median value.
- Inside the PLOT 3 a substantial decrease in the range of the estimates was attested in the post-training together with a detectable increase in the median value.
- In the PLOT 4 a slight decrease in the range of the estimates was found in the post-training together with an increase in the median value.

Nevertheless, the Wilcoxon test didn't attest statistically significant differences between the means of the observations before and after the intercalibration.

Furthermore, one outlier appeared for PLOT_1 for the post-training. That outlying point exceeds the IQR of 1.5 times and therefore was plotted outside the box plot.

Figure 36. Overall percentage cover for each plot (median is represented by the black cross line), calculated among the four teams between pre- and post-training exercises (2023). The pre-training interquartile range coloured in orange and the post-training coloured in green.

Considering the single pre-training exercise in 2023 (figure 37 & 38), the non-parametric Kruskal-Wallis test attested that there is no statistically significant difference between the surveyed plots for the overall percentage cover variable.

Overall cover box plot per plot for 2023 (Pre-training)

Figure 37. Overall % cover for each plot (median is represented by the black cross line), calculated among the four plots in the pre-training exercises (2023).

```
Kruskal-wallis rank sum test
data: total_cov by plot
Kruskal-wallis chi-squared = 1.1482, df = 3, p-value = 0.7655
```

Figure 38. Kruskal wallis for the pre-training exercise (2023) for each plot.

Considering the single post-training exercise in 2023 (figure 39 & 40), the non-parametric Kruskal-Wallis test attested that there is no statistically significant difference between the surveyed plots for the overall percentage cover variable.

Overall cover box plot per plot for 2023 (Post-training)

Figure 39. Overall % cover for each plot (median is represented by the black cross line), calculated among the four plots in the post-training exercises (2023).

```

Kruskal-wallis rank sum test
data: total_cov by plot
Kruskal-wallis chi-squared = 0.93608, df = 3, p-value = 0.8167

```

Figure 40. Kruskal wallis for the post-training exercise (2023) for each plot.

Considering the single post-training exercise in 2016 (figure 41 & 42), the non-parametric Kruskal-Wallis test attested that there is no statistically significant difference between the surveyed plots for the overall percentage cover variable.

Figure 41. Overall % cover for each plot (median is represented by the black cross line), calculated among the three plots in the post-training exercises (2016).

```
Kruskal-wallis rank sum test
data: total_cov by plot
Kruskal-wallis chi-squared = 2.5043, df = 2, p-value = 0.2859
```

Figure 42. Kruskal wallis for the post-training exercise (2016) for each plot.

Overall percentage cover between teams

Looking at the differences in the overall percentage cover, recorded by the four teams for the pre- and post- training exercises in 2023, it was detected that (figure 43):

- TEAM_32 displayed a decrease in the distance of the team estimates in the post-training, but the median value remained unchanged.
- TEAM_33 demonstrated a perceptible decrease in the range of the estimates in the post-training and an appreciable increase of the median.
- TEAM_34 showed a decrease in the range of estimates in the post-training and a sizable decrease of the median.
- TEAM_35 exhibited a drastic decrease in the range of the estimates in the post-training and a great increase in the median value.

In this case, the Wilcoxon test attested a statistically significant difference between the means of the observations before and after the intercalibration for the TEAM 35.

Furthermore, three outliers appeared for TEAM_32, 33, 35 in the post-training. Those outliers exceed the IQR of 1.5 times and were plotted individually.

Figure 43. Overall percentage cover for each team (median is represented by the black cross line), calculated among the four teams between pre- and post-training exercises (2023). The pre-training interquartile range coloured in orange and the post-training coloured in green.

Considering the single pre-training exercise in 2023 (figure 44 & 45), the non-parametric Kruskal-Wallis test attested that there is a statistically significant difference in the means between the teams. The Pariwise Wilcoxon Ranked Sum Test showed that this difference occurs between the TEAM 32 / TEAM 33, TEAM 32 / TEAM 35, TEAM 33 / TEAM 34 and TEAM 34 / TEAM 35.

Figure 44. Overall % cover for each team (median is represented by the black cross line), calculated among the four teams in the pre-training exercises (2023).

```

Kruskal-Wallis rank sum test

data: total_cov by team
Kruskal-Wallis chi-squared = 11.968, df = 3, p-value = 0.007492

Pairwise comparisons using wilcoxon rank sum test with continuity correction
data: data_lc_23_pre$total_cov and data_lc_23_pre$team

      team_32 team_33 team_34
team_33 0.027  -      -
team_34 0.304  0.027  -
team_35 0.028  0.874  0.027

P value adjustment method: none

```

Figure 45. Kruskal wallis and Pairwise Wilcoxon Rank Sum Test for the pre-training exercise (2023) for each team.

Considering the single post-training exercise in 2023 (figure 46 & 47), the non-parametric Kruskal-Wallis test attested that there is a statistically significant difference between the teams. The Pariwise Wilcoxon Ranked Sum Test showed that this difference occurs between TEAM 32 / TEAM 33, TEAM 32 / TEAM 35, TEAM 33 / TEAM 34, TEAM 33 / TEAM 35 and TEAM 34 / TEAM 35.

Figure 46. Overall % cover for each team (median is represented by the black cross line), calculated among the four teams in the post-training exercises (2023).

```

Kruskal-wallis rank sum test

data: total_cov by team
Kruskal-wallis chi-squared = 13.145, df = 3, p-value = 0.004334
Pairwise comparisons using wilcoxon rank sum test with continuity correction
data: data_lc_23_post$total_cov and data_lc_23_post$team

      team_32 team_33 team_34
team_33 0.023  -      -
team_34 0.180  0.026  -
team_35 0.023  0.058  0.026

P value adjustment method: none

```

Figure 47. Kruskal wallis and Pairwise Wilcoxon Rank Sum Test for the post-training exercise (2023) for each team.

Considering the single post-training exercise in 2016 (figure 48 & 49), the non-parametric Kruskal-Wallis test attested that there is no statistically significant difference between the surveyor teams for the overall percentage cover variable.

Figure 48. Overall % cover for each team (median is represented by the black cross line), calculated among the three teams in the post-training exercises (2016).

```

Kruskal-wallis rank sum test
data: total_cov by team
Kruskal-wallis chi-squared = 0.85797, df = 2, p-value = 0.6512
    
```

Figure 49. Kruskal wallis for the post-training exercise (2016) for each team.

3.4 TREE PERCENTAGE COVER

Tree percentage cover between plots

Looking at the differences in the tree percentage cover, recorded by the four teams for each plot for the pre- and post- training exercises in 2023, it was detected that (figure 50):

- Inside the PLOT_1 a drastic decrease in the range between the team estimates occurred in the post-training while the median value has greatly risen.
- In the PLOT 2 a drastic decrease in the range between the estimates was attested in the post-training together with an increase in the median value as well.
- Inside the PLOT 3 an increase in the range between the estimates occurred in the post-training together with an increase in the median value as well.
- In the PLOT 4 a dramatic increase in the range between the estimates was found in the post-training together with a large increase in the median value.

Nevertheless, the Wilcoxon test didn't attest statistically significant differences between the means of the observations before and after the intercalibration.

Furthermore, one outlier was found below the post-training data of the PLOT_1 and one below the pre-training data of the PLOT_3. Those data exceed the IQR of 1.5 times and were plotted outside the box plot.

Figure 50. Tree % cover for each plot (median is represented by the black cross line), calculated among the four plots between pre- and post-training exercises (2023). The pre-training interquartile range coloured in orange and the post-training coloured in green.

Considering the single pre-training exercise in 2023 (figure 51 & 52), the non-parametric Kruskal-Wallis test attested that there is no statistically significant difference between the surveyed plots for the tree percentage cover variable.

Figure 51. Tree % cover for each plot (median is represented by the black cross line), calculated among the four plots in the pre-training exercise (2023).

```
Kruskal-wallis rank sum test
data: tree_cov by plot
Kruskal-wallis chi-squared = 1.3215, df = 3, p-value = 0.724
```

Figure 52. Kruskal wallis for the pre-training exercise (2023) for each plot.

Considering the single post-training exercise in 2023 (figure 53 & 54), the non-parametric Kruskal-Wallis test attested that there is no statistically significant difference between the surveyed plots for the tree percentage cover variable.

Figure 53. Tree % cover for each plot (median is represented by the black cross line), calculated among the four plots in the post-training exercise (2023).

```

Kruskal-wallis rank sum test
data: tree_cov by plot
Kruskal-wallis chi-squared = 1.4013, df = 3, p-value = 0.7052

```

Figure 54. Kruskal wallis for the post-training exercise (2023) for each plot.

Considering the single post-training exercise in 2016 (figure 55 & 56), the non-parametric Kruskal-Wallis test attested that there is no statistically significant difference between the surveyed plots for the tree percentage cover variable.

Figure 55. Tree % cover for each plot (median is represented by the black cross line), calculated among the three plots in the post-training exercise (2016).

```
Kruskal-wallis rank sum test
data: tree_cov by plot
Kruskal-wallis chi-squared = 3.5862, df = 2, p-value = 0.1664
```

Figure 56. Kruskal wallis for the post-training exercise (2016) for each plot.

Tree percentage cover between teams

Looking at the differences in the tree percentage cover, recorded by the four teams for the pre- and post- training exercises in 2023, it was detected that (figure 57):

- TEAM_32 didn't show an appreciable variation in the range between the team estimates in the post-training, but the median value has arisen.
- TEAM_33 witnessed a slight increase in the range between the estimates in the post-training and an increase in the median value as well.
- TEAM_34 demonstrated a slight decrease in the range between the estimates in the post-training and an appreciable increase in the median.
- TEAM_35 exhibited a slight decrease in the range between the estimates in the post-training, but a large increase in the median value occurred.

The Wilcoxon test confirmed a statistically significant difference between the means of the observations before and after the intercalibration for the TEAM 35.

Differently from other variables, there is no data outlying point in this specific case.

Figure 57. Tree % cover for each team (median is represented by the black cross line), calculated among the four teams between pre- and post-training exercises (2023). The pre-training interquartile range coloured in orange and the post-training coloured in green.

Considering the single pre-training exercise in 2023 (figure 58 & 59), the non-parametric Kruskal-Wallis test attested that there is a statistically significant difference between the teams. The Pairwise Wilcoxon Rank Sum Test showed that this difference occurs between the TEAM_32 / TEAM_35 and TEAM_34 / TEAM_35.

Figure 58. Tree % cover for each team (median is represented by the black cross line), calculated among the four teams in the pre-training exercise (2023).

```

Kruskal-wallis rank sum test

data: tree_cov by team
Kruskal-wallis chi-squared = 11.754, df = 3, p-value = 0.008274
Pairwise comparisons using wilcoxon rank sum test with continuity correction

data: data_lc_23_pre$tree_cov and data_lc_23_pre$team

      team_32 team_33 team_34
team_33 0.086  -      -
team_34 0.178  0.052  -
team_35 0.027  0.086  0.027

P value adjustment method: none

```

Figure 59. Kruskal wallis and Pairwise Wilcoxon Rank Sum Test for the pre-training exercise (2023) for each team.

Considering the single post-training exercise in 2023 (figure 60 & 61), the non-parametric Kruskal-Wallis test attested that there is a statistically significant difference in the mean estimates between the teams. The Pairwise Wilcoxon Rank Sum Test showed that this difference occurs between the TEAM_33 / TEAM_34 and TEAM_34 / TEAM_35.

Figure 60. Tree % cover for each team (median is represented by the black cross line), calculated among the four teams in the post-training exercise (2023).

```

Kruskal-wallis rank sum test
data: tree_cov by team
Kruskal-wallis chi-squared = 7.7326, df = 3, p-value = 0.05187

```

Figure 61. Kruskal wallis for the post-training exercise (2023) for each team.

Considering the single post-training exercise in 2016 (figure 62 & 63), the non-parametric Kruskal-Wallis test attested that there is no statistically significant difference between the surveyor teams for the tree percentage cover variable.

Figure 62. Tree % cover for each team (median is represented by the black cross line), calculated among the three teams in the post-training exercise (2016).

```

Kruskal-wallis rank sum test
data: tree_cov by team
Kruskal-wallis chi-squared = 1.1954, df = 2, p-value = 0.5501

```

Figure 63. Kruskal wallis for the post-training exercise (2016) for each team.

3.5 SHRUB PERCENTAGE COVER

Shrub percentage cover between plots

Looking at the differences in the shrub percentage cover, recorded by the four teams for each plot for the pre- and post- training exercises in 2023, it was detected that (figure 64):

- Inside the PLOT_1 a substantial increase in the range between the team estimations was attested in the post-training while the median value has drastically reduced.
- In the PLOT_2 a drastic decrease in the range between the estimates was attested in the post-training together with a considerable decrease in the median value as well.
- Inside the PLOT_3 a dramatic decrease in the range between the estimates occurred in the post-training while the median value largely decreased.
- In the PLOT_4 an appreciable decrease in the range between the estimations was found in the post-training together with a large decrease in the median.

Nevertheless, the Wilcoxon test didn't attest statistically significant differences between the means of the observations before and after the intercalibration.

Three outliers were found: two below the pre-training exercise in PLOT_1 and PLOT_3 and the last one below the post-training in PLOT_4. These outlying points exceed 1.5 times the IQR and were plotted individually.

Figure 64. Shrub % cover for each plot (median is represented by the black cross line), calculated among the four plots between pre- and post-training exercises (2023). The pre-training interquartile range coloured in orange and the post-training coloured in green.

Considering the single pre-training exercise in 2023 (figure 65 & 66), the non-parametric Kruskal-Wallis test attested that there is no statistically significant difference between the monitored plots for the shrub percentage cover variable.

Figure 65. Shrub % cover for each plot (median is represented by the black cross line), calculated among the four plots in the pre-training exercise (2023).

```
kruskal-wallis rank sum test
data: shrub_cov by plot
Kruskal-wallis chi-squared = 1.1328, df = 3, p-value = 0.7692
```

Figure 66. Kruskal wallis for the pre-training exercise (2023) for each plot.

Considering the single post-training exercise in 2023 (figure 67 & 68), the non-parametric Kruskal-Wallis test attested that there is no statistically significant difference between the surveyed plots for the shrub percentage cover variable.

Shrub layer cover box plot per plot for 2023 (post-training)

Figure 67. Shrub % cover for each plot (median is represented by the black cross line), calculated among the four plots in the post-training exercise (2023).

```

Kruskal-wallis rank sum test
data: shrub_cov by plot
Kruskal-wallis chi-squared = 0.63522, df = 3, p-value = 0.8883
    
```

Figure 68. Kruskal wallis for the pre-training exercise (2023) for each plot.

Considering the single post-training exercise in 2016 (figure 69 & 70), the non-parametric Kruskal-Wallis test attested that there is no statistically significant difference between the monitored plots for the shrub percentage cover variable.

Figure 69. Shrub % cover for each plot (median is represented by the black cross line), calculated among the three plots in the post-training exercise (2016).

```

Kruskal-wallis rank sum test
data: shrub_cov by plot
Kruskal-wallis chi-squared = 0.83478, df = 2, p-value = 0.6588

```

Figure 70. Kruskal wallis for the pre-training exercise (2023) for each plot.

Shrub percentage cover between teams

Looking at the differences in the shrub percentage cover, recorded by the four teams for the pre- and post- training exercises in 2023, it was detected that (figure 71):

- TEAM_32 showed a drastic decrease in the range between the estimates in the post-training and the median value has drastically reduced as well.
- TEAM_33 displayed a limited decrease in the range between the estimations in the post-training but a dramatic decrease in the median value.
- TEAM_34 exhibited a strong decrease in the range between the esteems in the post-training and a large decrement in the median value.
- TEAM_35 attested a considerable increase in the range between the estimates in the post-training and an increase in the median value too.

The results of the Wilcoxon test are surprising: the test assessed the occurrence of statistically significant differences between the means of the observations before and after the intercalibration for all the four teams.

Three outliers were found: one above TEAM_33 for the pre-training and two for the TEAM_33 and TEAM_34 for the post-training. Those outliers exceed 1.5 times the IQR and were plotted individually.

Figure 71. Shrub % cover for each team (median is represented by the black cross line), calculated among the four teams between pre- and post-training exercises (2023). The pre-training interquartile range coloured in orange and the post-training coloured in green.

Considering the single pre-training exercise in 2023 (figure 72 & 73), the non-parametric Kruskal-Wallis test attested that there is a statistically significant difference in the means for the four plots sampled. The Pairwise Wilcoxon Ranked Sum Test illustrates that this difference occurs between the TEAM_32 / TEAM_35, TEAM_33 / TEAM_33, TEAM_34 / TEAM_35 for the shrub percentage cover variable.

Figure 72. Shrub % cover for each team (median is represented by the black cross line), calculated among the four teams in the pre-training exercise (2023).

```

Kruskal-wallis rank sum test

data: shrub_cov by team
Kruskal-wallis chi-squared = 10.737, df = 3, p-value = 0.01324
Pairwise comparisons using wilcoxon rank sum test with continuity correction

data: data_lc_23_pre$shrub_cov and data_lc_23_pre$team

      team_32 team_33 team_34
team_33 0.655  -      -
team_34 0.106  0.191  -
team_35 0.028  0.028  0.029

P value adjustment method: none

```

Figure 73. Kruskal wallis and Pairwise Wilcoxon Rank Sum Test for the pre-training exercise (2023) for each team.

Considering the single post-training exercise in 2023 (figure 74 & 75), the non-parametric Kruskal-Wallis test attested that there is a statistically significant difference in the means for the four plots sampled. The Pairwise Wilcoxon Ranked Sum Test illustrates that this difference occurs between the TEAM_32 / TEAM_33, TEAM_32 / TEAM_34, TEAM_32 / TEAM_35, TEAM_33 / TEAM_34 for the shrub percentage cover variable.

Figure 74. Shrub % cover for each team (median is represented by the black cross line), calculated among the four teams in the post-training exercise (2023).

```

Kruskal-wallis rank sum test

data: shrub_cov by team
Kruskal-Wallis chi-squared = 13.412, df = 3, p-value = 0.003825

Pairwise comparisons using Wilcoxon rank sum test with continuity correction
data: data_lc_23_post$shrub_cov and data_lc_23_post$team

      team_32 team_33 team_34
team_33 0.026  -      -
team_34 0.026  0.028  -
team_35 0.027  0.080  0.059

P value adjustment method: none

```

Figure 75. Kruskal wallis and Pairwise Wilcoxon Rank Sum Test for the post-training exercise (2023) for each team.

Considering the single post-training exercise in 2016 (figure 76 & 77), the non-parametric Kruskal-Wallis test attested that there is no statistically significant difference between the surveyor teams for the shrub percentage cover variable.

Figure 76. Shrub % cover for each team (median is represented by the black cross line), calculated among the three teams in the post-training exercise (2016).

```
Kruskal-wallis rank sum test
data: shrub_cov by team
Kruskal-wallis chi-squared = 4.4754, df = 2, p-value = 0.1067
```

Figure 77. Kruskal wallis for the post-training exercise (2016) for each team.

3.6 HERBACEOUS PERCENTAGE COVER

Herbaceous percentage cover between plots

Looking at the differences in the herbaceous percentage cover, recorded by the four teams for each plot for the pre- and post- training exercises in 2023, it was detected that (figure 78):

- Inside the PLOT_1 a decrease in the range between the team estimates occurred in the post-training while the median value has slightly reduced.
- In the PLOT_2 there was no appreciable variation in the range between the estimates between pre- and post-training, but a detectable decrease in the median value occurred.
- Inside the PLOT_3 a considerable decrease in the range between the estimations was attested in the post-training together with an evident increase in the median value.
- In the PLOT_4 a significant decrease in the range between the estimations occurred in the post-training together with a slight increase in the median value.

Nevertheless, the Wilcoxon test didn't attest statistically significant differences between the means of the observations before and after the intercalibration.

One outlier was found below the post-training exercise in PLOT_3. This outlying point exceeded the IQR of 1.5 times and was plotted individually.

Figure 78. Herbaceous % cover for each plot (median is represented by the black cross line), calculated among the four plots between pre- and post-training exercises (2023). The pre-training interquartile range coloured in orange and the post-training coloured in green.

Considering the single pre-training exercise in 2023 (figure 79 & 80), the non-parametric Kruskal-Wallis test attested that there is no statistically significant difference between the monitored plots for the herbaceous percentage cover variable.

Figure 79. Herbaceous % cover for each plot (median is represented by the black cross line), calculated among the four plots in the pre-training exercise (2023).

```

Kruskal-wallis rank sum test
data: herb_cov by plot
Kruskal-wallis chi-squared = 0.56667, df = 3, p-value = 0.904

```

Figure 80. Kruskal wallis and for the pre-training exercise (2023) for each plot.

Considering the single post-training exercise in 2023 (figure 81 & 82), the non-parametric Kruskal-Wallis test attested that there is no statistically significant difference between the monitored plots for the herbaceous percentage cover variable.

Figure 81. Herbaceous % cover for each plot (median is represented by the black cross line), calculated among the four plots in the post-training exercise (2023).

```
Kruskal-wallis rank sum test
data: herb_cov by plot
Kruskal-wallis chi-squared = 3.8225, df = 3, p-value = 0.2813
```

Figure 82. Kruskal wallis for the post-training exercise (2023) for each plot.

Considering the single post-training exercise in 2016 (figure 83 & 84), the non-parametric Kruskal-Wallis test attested that there is no statistically significant difference between the monitored plots for the herbaceous percentage cover variable.

Figure 83. Herbaceous % cover for each plot (median is represented by the black cross line), calculated among the three plots in the post-training exercise (2016).

```

Kruskal-wallis rank sum test

data: herb_cov by plot
Kruskal-wallis chi-squared = 5.3333, df = 2, p-value = 0.06948

```

Figure 84. Kruskal wallis for the post-training exercise (2016) for each plot.

Herbaceous percentage cover between teams

Looking at the differences in the herbaceous percentage cover, recorded by the four teams for the pre- and post- training exercises in 2023, it was detected that (figure 85):

- TEAM_32 displayed a slight increase in the range between the team estimates in the post-training, but the median value has appreciably reduced.
- TEAM_33 didn't display any difference for both the variation in the range between the appraisal between pre- and post-training and the median values.
- TEAM_34 attested a modest increase in the range between the estimations in the post-training, but an evident increase in the median occurred.
- TEAM_35 witnessed a slight decrease in the range between the estimates in the post-training and an appreciable decrease in the median.

Nevertheless, the Wilcoxon test didn't attest statistically significant differences between the means of the observations before and after the intercalibration.

Furthermore, no outliers were plotted in this specific case.

Figure 85. Herbaceous % cover for each team (median is represented by the black cross line), calculated among the four teams between pre- and post-training exercises (2023). The pre-training interquartile range coloured in orange and the post-training coloured in green.

Considering the single pre-training exercise in 2023 (figure 86 & 87), the non-parametric Kruskal-Wallis test attested that there is a statistically significant difference in the means between the team estimates. The Pairwise Wilcoxon Ranked Sum Test attested that this difference occurs between the TEAM_32 / TEAM_33, TEAM_32 / TEAM_34, TEAM_32 / TEAM_35, TEAM_33 / TEAM_34, TEAM_33 / TEAM_35, TEAM_34 / TEAM_35 for the herbaceous percentage cover variable. So, there was a great difference of estimates between the teams.

Figure 86. Herbaceous % cover for each team (median is represented by the black cross line), calculated among the four teams in the pre-training exercise (2023).

```

Kruskal-wallis rank sum test

data: herb_cov by team
Kruskal-wallis chi-squared = 14.05, df = 3, p-value = 0.002838
Pairwise comparisons using Wilcoxon rank sum test with continuity correction

data: data_lc_23_pre$herb_cov and data_lc_23_pre$team

      team_32 team_33 team_34
team_33 0.040  -      -
team_34 0.029  0.029  -
team_35 0.027  0.027  0.028

P value adjustment method: none

```

Figure 87. Kruskal wallis and Pairwise Wilcoxon Rank Sum Test for the pre-training exercise (2023) for each plot.

Considering the single post-training exercise in 2023 (figure 88 & 89), the non-parametric Kruskal-Wallis test attested that there is a statistically significant difference between TEAM_32 / TEAM_35, TEAM_33 / TEAM_35 for the herbaceous percentage cover variable.

Figure 88. Herbaceous % cover for each team (median is represented by the black cross line), calculated among the four teams in the post-training exercise (2023).

```

Kruskal-wallis rank sum test

data: herb_cov by team
Kruskal-wallis chi-squared = 9.1685, df = 3, p-value = 0.02713

Pairwise comparisons using wilcoxon rank sum test with continuity correction
data: data_lc_23_post$herb_cov and data_lc_23_post$team

      team_32 team_33 team_34
team_33 0.765  -      -
team_34 0.110  0.191  -
team_35 0.029  0.029  0.306

P value adjustment method: none

```

Figure 89. Kruskal wallis and Pairwise Wilcoxon Rank Sum Test for the post-training exercise (2023) for each plot.

Considering the single post-training exercise in 2016 (figure 90 & 91), the non-parametric Kruskal-Wallis test attested that there is no statistically significant difference between the surveyor teams for the herbaceous percentage cover variable.

Figure 90. Herbaceous % cover for each team (median is represented by the black cross line), calculated among the three teams in the post-training exercise (2016).

```

Kruskal-wallis rank sum test

data: herb_cov by team
Kruskal-wallis chi-squared = 2.1287, df = 2, p-value = 0.345

```

Figure 91. Kruskal wallis for the pre-training exercise (2016) for each plot.

3.7 LITTER PERCENTAGE COVER

Litter percentage cover between plots (SU)

Looking at the differences in the litter percentage cover, recorded by the four teams for each plot for the pre- and post- training exercises in 2023, it was detected that (figure 92):

- Inside the PLOT_1 there was no appreciable variation of the range between the team estimates in the post-training, but the median value has slightly augmented.
- In the PLOT_2 attested an appreciable decrement in the range between the estimations between pre- and post-training and an increase in the median value occurred.
- Inside the PLOT_3 there was no detectable variation in the range between the estimates in the post-training, but a slight increase in the median value occurred.
- In the PLOT_4 there was no appreciable variation in the range between the estimates in the post-training, but a slight decrement in the median value was attested.

Nevertheless, the Wilcoxon test didn't attest statistically significant differences between the means of the observations before and after the intercalibration.

Six outliers were detected between the different plots both for the pre- and post-training. These outlying points exceed the IQR of 1.5 times, thus they were plotted outside the box plot.

Figure 92. Litter % cover for each plot (median is represented by the black cross line), calculated among the four plots between pre- and post-training exercises (2023). The pre-training interquartile range coloured in orange and the post-training coloured in green.

Considering the single pre-training exercise in 2023 (figure 93 & 94), the non-parametric Kruskal-Wallis test attested that there is no statistically significant difference between the monitored plots for the litter percentage cover variable.

Figure 93. Litter % cover for each plot (median is represented by the black cross line), calculated among the four plots in the pre-training exercise (2023).

```
Kruskal-wallis rank sum test
data: litter by plot
Kruskal-wallis chi-squared = 0.039355, df = 3, p-value = 0.9979
```

Figure 94. Kruskal wallis for the pre-training exercise (2023) for each plot.

Considering the single post-training exercise in 2023 (figure 95 & 96), the non-parametric Kruskal-Wallis test attested that there is no statistically significant difference between the monitored plots for the litter percentage cover variable.

Figure 95. Litter % cover for each plot (median is represented by the black cross line), calculated among the four plots in the post-training exercise (2023).

```
Kruskal-wallis rank sum test
data: litter by plot
Kruskal-wallis chi-squared = 1.6302, df = 3, p-value = 0.6526
```

Figure 96. Kruskal wallis for the post-training exercise (2023) for each plot.

Considering the single post-training exercise in 2016 (figure 97 & 98), the non-parametric Kruskal-Wallis test attested that there is no statistically significant difference between the monitored plots for the litter percentage cover variable.

Figure 97. Litter % cover for each plot (median is represented by the black cross line), calculated among the three plots in the post-training exercise (2023).

```
Kruskal-wallis rank sum test
data: litter by plot
Kruskal-wallis chi-squared = 5.9556, df = 2, p-value = 0.05091
```

Figure 98. Kruskal wallis for the post-training exercise (2016) for each plot.

Litter percentage cover between teams

Looking at the differences in the litter percentage cover, recorded by the four teams for the pre- and post- training exercises in 2023, it was detected that (figure 99):

- TEAM_32 showed a slight decrease in the range between the estimates in the post-training and the median value has slightly augmented.
- TEAM_33 exhibited a substantial increment in the range of the estimations between pre- and post-training and the median value considerably increased as well.
- TEAM_34 demonstrated a slight decrement in the range between the appraisals in the post-training, but a slight increase in the median value occurred.
- TEAM_35 witnessed a perceptible increase in the range between the esteems in the post-training and an increase in the median value.

The Wilcoxon test determined a statistically significant difference between the means of the observations before and after the intercalibration for the TEAM 33 and TEAM 35.

Two outliers were detected: one for the TEAM_34 and one for the TEAM_35. These outlying points were exceeding the IQR of 1.5 times and were plotted outside the box plot.

Figure 99. Litter % cover for each team (median is represented by the black cross line), calculated among the four teams between pre- and post-training exercises (2023). The pre-training interquartile range coloured in orange and the post-training coloured in green.

Considering the single pre-training exercise in 2023 (figure 100 & 101), the non-parametric Kruskal-Wallis test attested that there is a statistically significant difference in the means between the survey teams for the litter percentage cover variable.

Particularly, the Pairwise Wilcoxon Rank Sum Test assessed that this difference occurs between the teams TEAM_32 / TEAM_33, TEAM_32 / TEAM_34, TEAM_33 / TEAM_34, TEAM_33 / TEAM_35, TEAM_34 / TEAM_35.

Figure 100. Litter % cover for each team (median is represented by the black cross line), calculated among the four teams in the pre-training exercise (2023).

```

Kruskal-wallis rank sum test

data: litter by team
Kruskal-wallis chi-squared = 13.156, df = 3, p-value = 0.004311

Pairwise comparisons using wilcoxon rank sum test with continuity correction

data: data_lc_23_pre$litter and data_lc_23_pre$team

      team_32 team_33 team_34
team_33 0.028  -      -
team_34 0.029  0.029  -
team_35 0.436  0.026  0.027

P value adjustment method: none

```

Figure 101. Kruskal wallis and Pairwise Wilcoxon Rank Sum Test for the pre-training exercise (2023) for each team.

Considering the single post-training exercise in 2023 (figure 102 & 103), the non-parametric Kruskal-Wallis test attested that there is a statistically significant difference in the means between the survey teams for the litter percentage cover variable.

Particularly, the Pairwise Wilcoxon Rank Sum Test assessed that this difference occurs between the teams: TEAM_32 / TEAM_33, TEAM_32 / TEAM_34, TEAM_33 / TEAM_34, TEAM_33 / TEAM_35.

Figure 102. Litter % cover for each team (median is represented by the black cross line), calculated among the four teams in the post-training exercise (2023).

```

Kruskal-wallis rank sum test

data: litter by team
Kruskal-wallis chi-squared = 11.656, df = 3, p-value = 0.008659

Pairwise comparisons using wilcoxon rank sum exact test

data: data_lc_23_post$litter and data_lc_23_post$team

      team_32 team_33 team_34
team_33 0.029  -      -
team_34 0.041  0.029  -
team_35 0.110  0.029  0.882

P value adjustment method: none
    
```

Figure 103. Kruskal wallis and Pairwise Wilcoxon Rank Sum Test for the post-training exercise (2023) for each team.

Considering the single post-training exercise in 2016 (figure 104 & 105), the non-parametric Kruskal-Wallis test attested that there is no statistically significant difference between the survey teams for the litter percentage cover variable.

Figure 104. Litter % cover for each team (median is represented by the black cross line), calculated among the three teams in the post-training exercise (2016).

```
Kruskal-wallis rank sum test
data: litter by team
Kruskal-wallis chi-squared = 1.6889, df = 2, p-value = 0.4298
```

Figure 105. Kruskal wallis for the post-training exercise (2016) for each team.

3.8 COEFFICIENT OF VARIATION FOR SPECIES RICHNESS

The analysis of the CV% for the variable “species richness” (figure 106) attested that the larger variability occurred in the T & I course of 2009, while the lowest CV% was found for the course in 2012. Nevertheless, a decreasing trend for the CV% values was attested after 2009, except for the T & I course in 2016, where a new peak of the CV% occurred.

Figure 106. Graph representing the CV% (on the y axis) and the T & I course for each year (on the x axis).

3.9 RESULTS OF THE FIELD CHECK

The field check was an activity forecasted by the Quality Assurance Program and so, included in the MODERnNEC schedule (Action B.3 & B.4).

The field check was performed by the control team Salvatori-Cervellini (team S-C) on the surveyor (team L-M) in the site of Cala Violina (25TOS2).

The following tables resume the outcomes of the control activity and highlight whether the outcome of the check confirmed the results of the training and intercalibration course.

In the plot number 8 (table 4), outside the fence of the LEVEL II ICP FOREST NETWORK only three variables observed at the field check didn't confirm the results of the course: shrub and herb percentage cover, number of tree species detected.

Thus, all the other variables confirmed the already acquired results at the training and intercalibration course.

It wasn't possible to evaluate whether the bare soil coverages confirmed the same outcomes of the course since this variable hasn't been analysed.

VARIABLES	VALUES S-C TEAM	VALUES L-M TEAM	CONFIRMATION OF POST-TRAINING & INTER-CALIBRATION RESULTS
Overall % cover	98 %	85 %	YES
Tree % cover	98 %	85 %	YES
Shrub % cover	1 %	1 %	NO
Herbaceous % cover	2 %	1 %	NO
Litter % cover	98 %	35 %	YES
Bare soil % cover	1 %	1 %	/
Number of arboreal species	2	2	NO
Number of shrub species	2	3	YES
Number of herbaceous species	6	7	YES
Number of total detected species	10	12	YES

Table 4. Results of the field check in Cava Violina for the plot 8-OUT.

In the plot number 11 (table 5), inner to the fence of the LEVEL II ICP FOREST NETWORK only three variables observed at the field check confirmed the results of the course: Overall percentage cover, tree percentage cover and litter percentage cover. Nevertheless, the shrub layer was absent within the two randomly selected SUs during the control and, therefore, it wasn't allowed to check for the variables regarding the shrub layer.

However, interesting outcomes emerged for most of the investigated variables: Herbaceous percentage cover, Number of arboreal species, Number of herbaceous species, Total number of detected species.

It wasn't possible to evaluate whether the bare soil coverages confirmed the same outcomes of the course since this variable hasn't been assessed.

VARIABLES	VALUES S-C TEAM	VALUES L-M TEAM	CONFIRMATION OF POST- TRAINING & INTER- CALIBRATION RESULTS
Overall % cover	98 %	95 %	YES
Tree % cover	97 %	95 %	YES
Shrub % cover	0	0	/
Herbaceous % cover	2 %	1 %	NO
Litter % cover	97 %	65 %	YES
Bare soil % cover	2 %	2 %	/
Number of arboreal species	2	2	NO
Number of shrub species	0	0	/
Number of herbaceous species	11	8	NO
Number of total detected species	13	10	NO

Table 5. Results of the field check in Cava Violina for the plot 11-IN.

4.0 DISCUSSION

Two ways can be applied to estimate the observer error in vegetation monitoring: Accuracy (the proximity of an estimate to the true value) and precision (the proximity of different observer estimates to each other). However, most studies lack an accuracy evaluation because it doesn't exist a way to estimate the true values in a natural environment, thus most studies elaborate analysis upon the precision (Morrison et al., 2016, Morrison & Young, 2016).

In my study case, I tried to evaluate the precision as well by comparing the range of estimates between observer teams and the median values for the analysed variables.

Concerning the **species richness** (figure 22 & 29, page 40 & 45), it is likely the most employed descriptor of plant diversity (Archaux et al., 2009).

In my study case a clear pattern wasn't established for the estimates of each team. Only in one plot (PLOT_1) and for one team (TEAM_33), there was a reduction in the estimate's range in the post-training. However, a higher average number of species was found in three plots (PLOT_1, 3, 4) over four in the post-training exercise. Similarly, three teams (TEAM_32, 34, 35) over four increased the average number of species detected in the post training than the pre-training. Nevertheless, the Wilcoxon-Mann-Whitney test didn't attested statistically significant differences between the means of estimates.

Although the Wilcoxon-Mann-Whitney test didn't find statistically significant differences between the means, the increase of the average number of species detected for three teams in the post-training may point out an effectiveness of the training and intercalibration course that allowed the observers to take confidence with the local flora and to detect more species in the post-training exercise. This hypothesis may confirm the suggestions of Morrison (2016) and Boch et al. (2022) which recommended the execution and, possibly, reiteration of training and intercalibration activities to reduce the observer error, despite there is still not a unilateral consensus about the effectiveness of the training activities. Indeed, Archaux et al. (2009) didn't find an appreciable effect of the observer training and intercalibration in the reduction of the error.

However, for my study, there was already a reference checklist of all the species detected at the T & I course in 2023. Thus, it could be possible in future to evaluate the real effectiveness of the course by measuring the accuracy rather than the precision for this "species richness" variable by comparing the results of the observers with those of the species checklist.

The main sources of observer error in the species individuation may be related to different factors. Archaux et al. (2009) reported that the overlooking rate (i.e. when species present are missed from the observer) increases when the

monitoring is performed by a single observer, while it is reduced when the species richness and the species relative cover increase. Similarly, Futschik et al. (2019), Morrison et al. (2020) and Boch et al. 2022 found that the relative cover of a species is one of the most influencing factors for the observer error: the rarest species are the ones to contribute the most to the overlooking error and, therefore, to the overall pseudoturnover.

Another aspect is of crucial importance: Morrison (2016) and Boch et al. (2022) pointed out that the pseudoturnover rate may vary between habitat types.

Therefore, the results obtained in my study are strongly specific to the conditions and factors of the T & I course such as the number of observers, the amount of rare species and their relative coverage, type of habitat, etc. So, in the future it could be interesting to investigate more in detail these aspects and how much each factor may affect the observer error.

Shifting to the variables dealing with the percentage covers of vegetation layers (overall, tree, shrub, herbaceous, litter), these ones resulted to be easier to understand and evaluate on the field with respect to the species richness. Indeed, differently from the species identification which require a long-term commitment to learn many plant species, the estimation of vegetation percentage covers seem more intuitive and easier variables to assess which are rather connected to the correct understanding of the monitoring protocols and to the personal perception of the observer.

For the **overall percentage cover** (figure 36 & 43, page 50 & 55), in the pre-training all the teams tended to overestimate this variable and in the post-training they reduced their attributions and tended to converge their estimations. So, there was a significant reduction in the estimates' range after the training and further, in all the four plots, it was found in average an increased attribution of the overall cover after the intercalibration session. Though, only two teams (TEAM_33, 35) increased as average the attributed values for the overall cover. So, substantial changes occurred after the intercalibration. However, the Wilcoxon-Mann-Whitney test attested a statistically significant difference only for the TEAM_35 between the pre- and post-training.

The results indicate that the training might have been effective for the survey teams, specifically for the TEAM_35 which tended to underestimate the overall cover before the intercalibration session, while after they increased their estimations converging toward the ones attributed by the other three teams.

Regarding the **tree percentage cover** (figure 50 & 57, page 60 & 65), only in two plots (PLOT_1, 2) over four the variability decreased in the post-training, whilst in the other two ones (PLOT_3, 4) it increased. Analysing the teams, it wasn't visually attested a considerable variability after the intercalibration session. However, it was found that the median values of the estimates from all the observers substantially increased in the post-training.

The Wilcoxon-Mann-Whitney test determined a statistically significant difference for the TEAM_35 between the pre- and post-training suggesting an efficacy of the formation session. The TEAM_35 instead tended to underestimate the tree cover in the pre-training, while in the post-training the observers increased their estimations and approached the estimates provided by the other teams.

Considering the **shrub percentage cover** (figure 64 & 71, page 70 & 75), for this variable the most interesting outcome surfaced. In three (PLOT_2, 3, 4) over four plots and for three (TEAM_32, 33, 34) over four teams, the range of observers estimates was strongly reduced in the post-training exercise. Furthermore, the median values were also strongly reduced in all the plots and for three (TEAM_32, 33, 34) over four teams after the intercalibration session.

The Wilcoxon-Mann-Whitney test confirmed statistically significant differences between the pre- and post-training for all the four teams suggesting drastic changes after the intercalibration.

The reason of a such data behaviour is related to a systematic error that emerged during the intercalibration session: the shrub layer was overestimated in the pre-training exercise because observers didn't pay attention to the peculiar case of the *Ruscus aculeatus* and considered it as a part of the shrub layer although it always belonged to the herbaceous one (although where it was exceeding 0.5 m of height). Thus, from this point of view, the course had a noticeable impact on the improving of the manual understanding and on the reduction of systematic errors.

Looking at the **herbaceous percentage cover** (figure 78 & 85, page 80 & 85), a decrease of the estimations range was attested in three plots (PLOT_1, 3, 4) over four, but it decreased only for one team (TEAM_35) over four after the intercalibration session. Similarly, the median values have only decreased in two plots (PLOT_3, 4) and for 2 teams (TEAM_32, 35) over four.

Nevertheless, the Wilcoxon-Mann-Whitney test didn't attest statistically significant differences between the means of estimations. These results may suggest that this variable was already well-understood before the intercalibration session.

However, these data aren't unequivocal. Indeed, whether the shrub layer decreased in its cover after the intercalibration because of the *Ruscus aculeatus* case, then an increase in the cover of the herbaceous layer was expected as a consequence of the consideration of the *Ruscus aculeatus* in this layer. However, this behaviour just partly appeared in the PLOT_3 and PLOT_4 and TEAM_34.

Concerning the **litter percentage cover** (figure 92 & 99, page 90 & 95), this variable wasn't treated at the training and intercalibration course in 2023. However, I performed the analysis for this variable a posteriori. My analysis attested that the range of estimates didn't largely change between the pre- and post-training in the four plots, but the median values of the estimations increased in three plots (PLOT_1, 2, 3) over four. However, looking at the teams, the range

of the estimates decreased only for two teams (TEAM_32, 34) over four in the post-training, but the median values increased for all the teams in the post-training.

The Wilcoxon-Mann-Whitney test determined statistically significant differences between the pre- and post-training for the TEAM_33 and TEAM_35.

Nevertheless, it was fundamental to point out the result surfaced from the TEAM_33: it widely underestimated the litter cover with respect to the other three teams. Looking also at the figure 89, 6 outliers appeared. These outliers are likely related to the estimates provided by the TEAM_33 and this confirms the underestimation of the litter cover from these observers. This aspect also emerged at the field check of Cala Violina with the monitoring team (L-M) that was TEAM_33 at the T & I course (2023). The reason for such behaviour was related to a misunderstanding of the monitoring protocol for this variable. Indeed, during the field check, it was found that the TEAM_33 didn't consider the dead standing tree trunk as components of the litter. So, they strongly underestimated the litter percentage cover.

Further, it's interesting to point out that the TEAM_33 didn't overestimate the tree percentage cover, despite considering the dead standing tree trunks in this layer.

This may furtherly confirm that the monitoring through visible observation is strongly related to the personal perception of the human observer and that any data coming from this kind of survey probably include a given degree of uncertainty (Milberg Per et al., 2008, Boch et al., 2022). Thus, it doesn't matter how much workers try to standardise the monitoring: there will always be a degree of error caused by systematic errors (when a particular person notoriously over- or under-estimates the actual cover of species or of another variable) or random (fluctuate among subsequent estimates of species cover or of another variable, either of one and the same observer or among different observers) errors (Futshik et al., 2018) that may cause a shift from the true value (Gorrod & Keith, 2009).

This is why it is so crucial to develop a precise quality assurance program with a formation process for the surveyor, practices of control and actions to monitor and assess the possible observer error and the sources of such error.

Though, the field check demonstrated its effectiveness: during the control activity, it was detected that the systematic error related to the litter percentage cover that didn't come to surface at the T & I course. Thus, the combination of formation courses together with control activities is winning and allows an improvement of the monitoring practice for future survey campaigns (e.g. the one forecasted in 2024 for the MODERnNEC).

Notwithstanding, there are some considerations to do about the field check: the peculiarities and characteristics of the vegetation in Cava Violina site was different from the Marsiliana, where the training session was held. Furthermore,

only two SUs were sampled during the field check, thus the control activity wasn't truly representative of the survey site. In addition, the survey team L-M worked for a day and half before the control. This may have caused an accumulation of tiredness, and the hurry to finish all the monitoring activities foreseen by the MODERnNEC may have altered the results of the control activity.

So, in the future it could be evaluated to improve the field check by increasing the number of controlled SUs and to perform the control activity on more than one team to increase the chance of detection for errors.

Looking at the training and intercalibration session, it brought at surface relevant evidence concerning some critical aspects of the manual, of the sampling procedures themselves but also about the conduction of the training session. It was useful to standardise the survey of the cover percentage variables to detect the systematic error related to the *Ruscus aculeatus* case and probably to better fix the local flora at the Marsiliana.

Nevertheless, it would be appropriate to improve some aspect of the T & I course:

- To treat more variables (e.g. litter coverage) during this session.
- To spend more time on the observer formation for plant species recognition.

I didn't find many articles dealing with the evaluation of observer error for the variables related to the covers of vegetation elements. Most of the studies only focused on the error of estimation for the relative cover of the single species (Allegrini et al., 2008, Morrison et al., 2016, Morrison & Young 2016, Boch et al., 2022).

Nevertheless, Allegrini et al., 2008 assessed the range of variability of team estimates for the tree, shrub, herb and moss vegetation layer within the ICP forest program through the Index of Coverage (ICR). Allegrini et al., 2008 found that after the training and intercalibration the estimations of the cover values decreased and tended to converge suggesting the effectiveness of the T & I course.

Moreover, in Australia, Kenny et al. (2011) worked on the estimation of different variables after among which the canopy cover, subcanopy cover, shrub cover, native perennial grass cover, and the litter cover by using measures of dispersion such as the standard deviation, the interquartile range, the coefficient of variation and the quartile coefficient of dispersion. In the study, Kenny et al. (2011) tested observers after a training course, and they found that all the variables of interest showed some variability.

Further, Johns et al. (2015) investigated the observer error for the visual cover estimates on the Australian wetlands for each vascular plant species, percentage cover of bare ground and open water, percentage cover of live green (i.e.

photosynthetic) vegetation and dead/senescent vegetation. Johns et al. (2015) attested some degree of variability between the observer estimates mostly depending upon the cover type and whether the same or different observers were used each time.

So, also for the variables concerning the cover of vegetation elements, differences between observers may be attested and therefore, these aspects need to be more investigated and implemented in future.

Finally, looking at the CV% for the species richness (figure 106, page 99), a higher variability of estimates was assessed in 2016 rather than in 2023.

However, between the course in 2016 and 2023 observers changed, sites changed, period of survey varied. Thus, these factors may have characterised the results of each course.

Furthermore, there was an observer who participated in both the 2016 and 2023 exercises. We would expect him to be more prepared to read and comprehend the manual, as well as to better recognize the species in 2023 than in 2016. However, this assumption didn't find clear evidence from the intercalibration exercise.

The analysis of the percentage coefficient of variation (CV%) for the five T & I courses (figure 106, page 99) showed a general decreasing trend from 2009 to 2023 in the variability of species richness assessment, except for the T & I course in 2016 where the CV% increased.

Allegrini et al., 2008 attested a similar outcome of the CV% between the T & I course in 2002, 2003, 2005 and 2006 which showed a decreasing trend of the CV% year by year and suggesting a possible cogency of the training.

Furthermore, Morrison (2016) and Boch et al. (2022) also suggested that the reiteration of training activities may be effective in the reduction of observer error.

The hypothesis isn't only regarding the simple reiteration of the T & I courses with time but, further, it is also connected to the structure of the course itself and to the simplification and the perfecting of the field manuals, survey practises and T & I courses performance. This might have brought a reduction of systematic errors and a better understanding of the sampling protocol for the observers causing a reduction of the variability.

Quality assurance program for long-term projects (*Allegrini et al., 2009*) it's a ceaseless and ongoing process that guarantees given and well-known quality standards at each monitoring session. However, it needs a continual update to be efficient, implying the reiteration of the steps provided by the QA Program itself. This opens new frontiers for the improvement and occurrence of further training and intercalibration courses and the application of new field checks in

the next monitoring campaigns scheduled in 2024. These tools were proved to be effective under different circumstances and may be replicated in future.

5.0 CONCLUSIONS

The low numbers of available observations in the datasets didn't allow me to perform the pseudoturnover measurement because it could have been an unreliable tool. Therefore, I decided to rely on the IQR variability of the estimations and on the differences in the means (attested via Wilcoxon test).

During 2024 a new monitoring campaign will be performed within the MODERnNEC project. This can open the chance for new field checks and to evaluate eventual variations with respect to the monitoring campaign in 2023. The manual developed in 2023 will be updated and implemented with a new set of indicators and with further modifications to improve the structures and the explanations of the activities.

Furthermore, a new training and intercalibration course will likely be scheduled in 2025 for the new Italian National Inventory and this could enhance the available data for new analysis about the observer error.

In addition, from the previous T & I courses (2009, 2011, 2012), many data are still available and their analysis may open to new frontiers in the study of the intra- and inter-observer error.

6.0 ADDITIONAL MATERIALS: R SCRIPTS FOR THE STATISTICAL ANALYSIS

Script 00 - Loading script 01a and 02b were the data wrangling was performed for 2016 and 2023

```
# SCRIPT 00 - RUN SCRIPT 01 AND LOAD DATA WITH SOME PACKAGES
```

```
rm(list=ls())
```

```
setwd("C:/Users/Leonardo/Desktop/2308 Quality assurance training/02_R Project/2308 Quality assurance training")
```

```
# Loading data prepared in the Script 01_A -
```

```
species_data_management_2016_2023_diversity
```

```
source("C:/Users/Leonardo/Desktop/2308 Quality assurance training/02_R Project/2308
```

```
Quality assurance training/Script/Code/Leonardo
```

```
scripts/01_A_species_data_management_2016_2023_diversity.R")
```

```
# Loading data prepared in the Script 01_B - species_data_management_2016_2023_cover
```

```
source("C:/Users/Leonardo/Desktop/2308 Quality assurance training/02_R Project/
```

2308 Quality assurance training/Script/Code/Leonardo
scripts/01_B_species_data_management_2016_2023_cover.R")

Script 01a - Loading data for species richness and data wrangling for 2016 and 2023

SCRIPT 01 - DATA MANIPULATION FOR DIVERSITY ----

```
rm(list=ls())
```

```
library(tidyverse)
```

```
library(readxl)
```

```
setwd("C:/Users/Leonardo/Desktop/2308 Quality assurance training/02_R Project/2308  
Quality assurance training")
```

```
# Load data
```

```
data_sp_16 <- read_xls("C:/Users/Leonardo/Desktop/2308 Quality assurance training/02_R  
Project/2308 Quality assurance training/Data/2016/Post training/16CopSNN.xls")
```

```
data_sp_23 <- read_xls("C:/Users/Leonardo/Desktop/2308 Quality assurance training/02_R  
Project/2308 Quality assurance training/Data/2023/Post training/23CopSNN.xls")
```

```
# Data wrangling ----
```

```
table(data_sp_16$"Plot number")
```

```
table(data_sp_16$"In/Out")
```

```
table(data_sp_23$"Plot number")
```

```
table(data_sp_23$"In/Out")
```

```
## Set up the column names and eliminate some variables ----
```

```
data_sp_16`Id Plot` <- NULL
```

```
data_sp_16$Notes <- NULL
```

```
data_sp_16`In/Out` <- NULL
```

```
data_sp_16`Spring/Summer` <- NULL
```

```
colnames(data_sp_16) <- c(  
  "date", "team", "Plot",  
  "layer_id", "species",  
  "cover_B-B", "percentage_cover"
```

```
)
```

```
data_sp_23`Id Plot` <- NULL
```

```
data_sp_23$Notes <- NULL
```

```
data_sp_23`In/Out` <- NULL
```

```
data_sp_23`Spring/Summer` <- NULL
```

```
colnames(data_sp_23) <- c(  
  "date", "team", "Plot",  
  "layer_id", "species",  
  "cover_B-B", "percentage_cover"
```

```
)
```

```
## Sorting data ----
```

```
data_sp_16 <- data_sp_16[
```

```
,
```

```
  order(  
    match(  
      data_sp_16$
```

```
      "date",  
      data_sp_23$
```

```

    colnames(data_sp_16),
    c(
      "date", "team", "Plot",
      "layer_id", "species",
      "cover_B-B", "percentage_cover"
    )
  )
)
]

```

```

data_sp_23 <- data_sp_23[
,
order(
  match(
    colnames(data_sp_23),
    c(
      "date", "team", "Plot",
      "layer_id", "species",
      "cover_B-B", "percentage_cover"
    )
  )
)
]

```

code the layers intuitively ----

```

table(data_sp_16$layer_id)
str(data_sp_16$layer_id)
data_sp_16$layer_id = as.factor(data_sp_16$layer_id)

```

```

table(data_sp_23$layer_id)
str(data_sp_23$layer_id)
data_sp_23$layer_id = as.factor(data_sp_23$layer_id)

```

Layer codes meaning

#1 tree (woody + pertinent lianas and climbers) $h > 5$ m

#2 shrub (woody + pertinent lianas and climbers) $0,5 < h \leq 5$

#3 herb (however herbaceous and ferns; woody only if $h \leq 0.5$ m) $h \leq 0,5$ m

#4 moss (terricolous bryophytes and t-lichens) on mineral, organic soil

```

data_sp_16 <- data_sp_16 |>

```

```

mutate(
  layer_id = recode(
    layer_id,
    "1" = "tree",
    "2" = "shrub",
    "3" = "herb",
    "4" = "moss"
  )
)

```

```

data_sp_23 <- data_sp_23 |>
  mutate(
    layer_id = recode(
      layer_id,
      "1" = "tree",
      "2" = "shrub",
      "3" = "herb",
      "4" = "moss"
    )
  )

```

In the case of white space

```
data_sp_16$species |> trimws()
```

```
data_sp_23$species |> trimws()
```

adding survey event with the same values of team variable ----

```
data_sp_16$event <- as.factor(data_sp_16$team)
```

```
data_sp_23$event <- as.factor(data_sp_23$team)
```

Changing values in event column with post training ----

```

data_sp_16 <- data_sp_16 |>
  mutate(
    event = recode(
      event,
      "91" = "post_training",
      "92" = "post_training",
      "93" = "post_training",
    )
  )

```

```
data_sp_23 <- data_sp_23 %>%
```

```

  mutate(
    event = recode(
      event,
      "32" = "pre_training",
      "33" = "pre_training",
      "34" = "pre_training",
      "35" = "pre_training",
      "36" = "post_training",
      "37" = "post_training",
      "38" = "post_training",
      "39" = "post_training"
    )
  )

```

Filtering pre-training observation and creating pre-training data set

```

data_sp_23_pre <- data_sp_23 |>
  dplyr::filter(event == "pre_training")

```

```
## Removing pre_training and filtering only post-training observations in data_sp_23 ----
data_sp_23_post <- data_sp_23 |>
  dplyr::filter(event == "post_training")
```

```
## Uniforming team code of pre- and post-training
```

```
data_sp_23_post <- data_sp_23_post %>%
  mutate(
    team = recode(
      team,
      "36" = "32",
      "37" = "33",
      "38" = "34",
      "39" = "35",
    )
  )
```

```
# PRE- AND POST-TRAINING TOGETHER (2023) ----
```

```
data_pre_post_2023 <- read_xlsx("C:/Users/Leonardo/Desktop/2308 Quality assurance
training/02_R Project/2308 Quality assurance training/Data/data_pre_post_2023.xlsx")
```

```
## Adding a further column called "event"
```

```
data_pre_post_2023$event <- as.factor(data_pre_post_2023$team)
```

```
data_pre_post_2023 <- data_pre_post_2023 %>%
```

```
  mutate(
    event = recode(
      event,
      "32" = "pre_training",
      "33" = "pre_training",
      "34" = "pre_training",
      "35" = "pre_training",
      "36" = "post_training",
      "37" = "post_training",
      "38" = "post_training",
      "39" = "post_training"
    )
  )
```

```
## Managing the column "team"
```

```
data_pre_post_2023 <- data_pre_post_2023 %>%
```

```
  dplyr::select(team, plot, spp_richness, Shannon_index, Simpson_index, event) %>%
  mutate(
    team = recode(
      team,
      "32" = "32",
      "33" = "33",
      "34" = "34",
      "35" = "35",
      "36" = "32",
      "37" = "33",
      "38" = "34",
      "39" = "35"
    )
  )
```

```

)
)

data_pre_post_2023 <- data_pre_post_2023 %>%
  mutate(
    team = recode(
      team,
      "32" = "team_32",
      "33" = "team_33",
      "34" = "team_34",
      "35" = "team_35",
    )
  )
)

```

Script 01b - Loading data for layer cover and data wrangling for 2016 and 2023

SCRIPT 01_B - DATA MANIPULATION FOR LAYER COVER ----

```
rm(list=ls())
```

```
library(tidyverse)
```

```
library(readxl)
```

```
setwd("C:/Users/Leonardo/Desktop/2308 Quality assurance training/02_R Project/2308  
Quality assurance training")
```

Load data

```
data_lc_16 <- read_xlsx("C:/Users/Leonardo/Desktop/2308 Quality assurance training/02_R  
Project/2308 Quality assurance training/Data/2016/Post training/16CopLNN.xlsx")
```

```
data_lc_23 <- read_xlsx("C:/Users/Leonardo/Desktop/2308 Quality assurance training/02_R  
Project/2308 Quality assurance training/Data/2023/Post training/23CopLNN.xls")
```

Data wrangling ----

Set up the column names and eliminate some variables ----

2016

```
data_lc_16$`Id Plot` <- NULL
```

```
data_lc_16$`In/Out` <- NULL
```

```
data_lc_16$`Spring/Summer` <- NULL
```

```
data_lc_16$Notes <- NULL
```

```
data_lc_16$`Tree height` <- NULL
```

```
data_lc_16$`Mosses cover` <- NULL
```

```
colnames(data_lc_16) <- c(
```

```
  "date", "team", "plot",
```

```
  "total_cov", "tree_cov", "shrub_ht",
```

```
  "shrub_cov", "herb_ht", "herb_cov",
```

```
  "litter", "baresoil"
```

```
)
```

2023

```
data_lc_23$`Id Plot` <- NULL
```

```
data_lc_23$`In/Out` <- NULL
```

```
data_lc_23$`Spring/Summer` <- NULL
```

```
data_lc_23$Notes <- NULL
```

```
data_lc_23$`Tree height` <- NULL
```

```

data_lc_23$`Mosses cover` <- NULL
colnames(data_lc_23) <- c(
  "date", "team", "plot",
  "total_cov", "tree_cov", "shrub_ht",
  "shrub_cov", "herb_ht", "herb_cov",
  "litter", "baresoil"
)
## sorting data
data_lc_16 <- data_lc_16[
,
order(
  match(
    colnames(data_lc_16),
    c("date", "team", "plot",
      "total_cov", "tree_cov", "shrub_ht",
      "shrub_cov", "herb_ht", "herb_cov",
      "litter", "baresoil"
    )
  )
)
]

data_lc_23 <- data_lc_23[
,
order(
  match(
    colnames(data_lc_23),
    c("date", "team", "plot",
      "total_cov", "tree_cov", "shrub_ht",
      "shrub_cov", "herb_ht", "herb_cov",
      "litter", "baresoil"
    )
  )
)
]
## adding survey event with the same values of team variable ----
data_lc_16$event <- as.factor(data_lc_16$team)

data_lc_23$event <- as.factor(data_lc_23$team)
## Changing values in event column with post training ----
data_lc_16 <- data_lc_16 |>
mutate(
  event = recode(
    event,
    "91" = "post_training",
    "92" = "post_training",
    "93" = "post_training",
  )
)

```

```

data_lc_23 <- data_lc_23 %>%
  mutate(
    event = recode(
      event,
      "32" = "pre_training",
      "33" = "pre_training",
      "34" = "pre_training",
      "35" = "pre_training",
      "36" = "post_training",
      "37" = "post_training",
      "38" = "post_training",
      "39" = "post_training"
    )
  )

```

Changing content of team and plot columns

data_lc_16

```

data_lc_16 <- data_lc_16 %>%
  mutate(
    team = recode(
      team,
      "91" = "team_91",
      "92" = "team_92",
      "93" = "team_93"
    )
  )

```

```

data_lc_16 <- data_lc_16 %>%
  mutate(
    plot = recode(
      plot,
      "1" = "plot_1",
      "2" = "plot_2",
      "3" = "plot_3"
    )
  )

```

data_lc_23

```

data_lc_23 <- data_lc_23 %>%
  mutate(
    team = recode(
      team,
      "32" = "32",
      "33" = "33",
      "34" = "34",
      "35" = "35",
      "36" = "32",
      "37" = "33",
      "38" = "34",

```

```

    "39" = "35"
  )
)

data_lc_23 <- data_lc_23 %>%
  mutate(
    team = recode(
      team,
      "32" = "team_32",
      "33" = "team_33",
      "34" = "team_34",
      "35" = "team_35",
    )
  )

data_lc_23 <- data_lc_23 %>%
  mutate(
    plot = recode(
      plot,
      "1" = "plot_1",
      "2" = "plot_2",
      "3" = "plot_3",
      "4" = "plot_4"
    )
  )
## Filtering pre-training observation and creating pre-training data set
data_lc_23_pre <- data_lc_23 |>
  dplyr::filter(event == "pre_training")
## Removing pre_training and filtering only post-training observations in data_sp_23 ----
data_lc_23_post <- data_lc_23 |>
  dplyr::filter(event == "post_training")
## Changing content of team and plot columns
### data_lc_23_pre
data_lc_23_pre <- data_lc_23_pre %>%
  mutate(
    team = recode(
      team,
      "32" = "team_32",
      "33" = "team_33",
      "34" = "team_34",
      "35" = "team_35"
    )
  )

data_lc_23_pre <- data_lc_23_pre %>%
  mutate(
    plot = recode(
      plot,
      "1" = "plot_1",

```

```

    "2" = "plot_2",
    "3" = "plot_3",
    "4" = "plot_4"
  )
)
### data_lc_23_post
data_lc_23_post <- data_lc_23_post %>%
  mutate(
    team = recode(
      team,
      "36" = "team_36",
      "37" = "team_37",
      "38" = "team_38",
      "39" = "team_39"
    )
  )

data_lc_23_post <- data_lc_23_post %>%
  mutate(
    plot = recode(
      plot,
      "1" = "plot_1",
      "2" = "plot_2",
      "3" = "plot_3",
      "4" = "plot_4"
    )
  )

```

Script 02 - Species richness calculation, box plots elaboration and Kruskal-Wallis test for the pre-training and post-training in 2023 and the post-training in 2016

```

library(tidyverse)
library(labdsv)
library(vegan)
library(ggpubr)

##* 2016: POST-TRAINING ----
## 2.0 - SPECIES RICHNESS (VEGAN PREPARATION) ----
## Species richness as a whole 2016 (post-training)
matr_sp_16 <- data_sp_16 |>
  dplyr::select(Plot, species, percentage_cover)
matr_sp_16 <- matr_sp_16 |> as.data.frame()

matr_sp_16 <- matr_sp_16 |> matrifify()

specpool(matr_sp_16)

nspp_16 <- specnumber(matr_sp_16)

```

```

## Species richness for each team and plot 2016
matr_sp_16_2.0 <- data_sp_16 |>
  dplyr::select(team, Plot, species, percentage_cover)

matr_sp_16_2.0 <- matr_sp_16_2.0 |>
  unite(team_plot, c(team, Plot))

matr_sp_16_2.0 <- matr_sp_16_2.0 |> as.data.frame()
matr_sp_16_2.0 <- matr_sp_16_2.0 |> matrifify()

nsp_16_post_team_plot <- specnumber(matr_sp_16_2.0)
## 2.1 - BOX PLOTS RICHNESS ----
Dataset_spp_richness_2016 <- read_xlsx("C:/Users/Leonardo/Desktop/2308 Quality
assurance training/02_R Project/2308 Quality assurance
training/Data/Dataset_spp_richness_2016.xlsx")
## Box plot Species richness for each team for 2016
box_plot_rich_16 <- Dataset_spp_richness_2016 |>
  ggplot(aes(x = team, y = spp_richness, fill = team)) +
  stat_boxplot(geom = "errorbar") +
  geom_boxplot() +
  theme_bw() +
  theme(legend.position = "none") +
  ylab("SPECIES RICHNESS") +
  xlab("TEAM") +
  ggtitle("Species richness for 2016")

ggsave("Box_plot_spp_rich_2016.jpeg", box_plot_rich_16,
  width = 180,
  height = 180,
  units = "mm")
## kruskal-wallis & Pairwise Wilcoxon Rank Sum Test
kruskal.test(spp_richness~team, data = Dataset_spp_richness_2016)

pairwise.wilcox.test(Dataset_spp_richness_2016$spp_richness,
  Dataset_spp_richness_2016$team, p.adjust.method = "none")
## Box plot Species richness for each plot for 2016
box_plot_rich_16_plot <- Dataset_spp_richness_2016 |>
  ggplot(aes(x = plot, y = spp_richness, fill = plot)) +
  stat_boxplot(geom = "errorbar") +
  geom_boxplot() +
  theme_bw() +
  theme(legend.position = "none") +
  ylab("SPECIES RICHNESS") +
  xlab("PLOTS") +
  ggtitle("Species richness for 2016")

ggsave("Box_plot_spp_rich_2016_plot.jpeg", box_plot_rich_16_plot,
  width = 180,
  height = 180,

```

```

units = "mm")
## kruskal-wallis & Pairwise Wilcoxon Rank Sum Test
kruskal.test(spp_richness~plot, data = Dataset_spp_richness_2016)

pairwise.wilcox.test(Dataset_spp_richness_2016$spp_richness,
Dataset_spp_richness_2016$plot, p.adjust.method = "none")

##* 2023: PRE-TRAINING ----
## 2.0 - SPECIES RICHNESS (VEGAN PREPARATION) ----
## Species richness as a whole 2023 (pre-training)
matr_sp_23_pre <- data_sp_23_pre |>
  dplyr::select(Plot, species, percentage_cover)

matr_sp_23_pre <- matr_sp_23_pre |> as.data.frame()

matr_sp_23_pre <- matr_sp_23_pre |> matrifify()

specpool(matr_sp_23_pre)

nsp_23_pre <- specnumber(matr_sp_23_pre)
## Species richness for each team and plot 2023 (pre-training)
matr_sp_23_pre_2.0 <- data_sp_23_pre |>
  dplyr::select(team, Plot, species, percentage_cover)

matr_sp_23_pre_2.0 <- matr_sp_23_pre_2.0 |>
  unite(team_plot, c(team, Plot))

matr_sp_23_pre_2.0 <- matr_sp_23_pre_2.0 |> as.data.frame()
matr_sp_23_pre_2.0 <- matr_sp_23_pre_2.0 |> matrifify()

specpool(matr_sp_23_pre_2.0)
nsp_23_pre_team_plot <- specnumber(matr_sp_23_pre_2.0)

## 2.1 - BOX PLOTS RICHNESS ----
Dataset_spp_richness_pre_2023 <- read_xlsx("C:/Users/Leonardo/Desktop/2308 Quality
assurance training/02_R Project/2308 Quality assurance
training/Data/Dataset_spp_richness_pre_2023.xlsx")
## Box plot Species richness for each team for 2023 PRE-TRAINING
box_plot_rich_23_pre <- Dataset_spp_richness_pre_2023 |>
  ggplot(aes(x = team, y = spp_richness, fill = team)) +
  stat_boxplot(geom = "errorbar") +
  geom_boxplot() +
  theme_bw() +
  theme(legend.position = "none") +
  ylab("Species richness") +
  ggtitle("Species richness box plot for 2023 (pre-training)")

ggsave("Box_plot_spp_rich_2023_pre.jpeg", box_plot_rich_23_pre,
width = 180,

```

```

    height = 180,
    units = "mm")
## kruskal-wallis & Pairwise Wilcoxon Rank Sum Test
kruskal.test(spp_richness~team, data = Dataset_spp_richness_pre_2023)

pairwise.wilcox.test(Dataset_spp_richness_pre_2023$spp_richness,
Dataset_spp_richness_pre_2023$team, p.adjust.method = "none")
## Box plot Species richness for each plot for 2023 PRE-TRAINING
box_plot_rich_23_pre_plot <- Dataset_spp_richness_pre_2023 |>
  ggplot(aes(x = plot, y = spp_richness, fill = plot)) +
  stat_boxplot(geom = "errorbar") +
  geom_boxplot() +
  theme_bw() +
  theme(legend.position = "none") +
  ylab("Species richness") +
  ggtitle("Species richness box plot per plot for 2023 (pre-training)")

ggsave("Box_plot_spp_rich_2023_pre_per_plot.jpeg", box_plot_rich_23_pre_plot,
  width = 180,
  height = 180,
  units = "mm")
## kruskal-wallis & Pairwise Wilcoxon Rank Sum Test
kruskal.test(spp_richness~plot, data = Dataset_spp_richness_pre_2023)

pairwise.wilcox.test(Dataset_spp_richness_pre_2023$spp_richness,
Dataset_spp_richness_pre_2023$plot, p.adjust.method = "none")

#* 2023: POST-TRAINING ----
## 2.0 - SPECIES RICHNESS (VEGAN PREPARATION) ----
## Species richness as a whole 2023 (post-training)
matr_sp_23_post <- data_sp_23_post |>
  dplyr::select(Plot, species, percentage_cover)

matr_sp_23_post <- matr_sp_23_post |> as.data.frame()

matr_sp_23_post <- matr_sp_23_post |> matrifify()

specpool(matr_sp_23_post)

nspp_23_post <- specnumber(matr_sp_23_post)

## Species richness for each team and plot 2023 POST_TRAINING
matr_sp_23_2.0 <- data_sp_23_post |>
  dplyr::select(team, Plot, species, percentage_cover)

matr_sp_23_2.0 <- matr_sp_23_2.0 |>
  unite(team_plot, c(team, Plot))

matr_sp_23_2.0 <- matr_sp_23_2.0 |> as.data.frame()

```

```

matr_sp_23_2.0 <- matr_sp_23_2.0 |> matrifify()

specpool(matr_sp_23_2.0)

nspp_23_2.0 <- specnumber(matr_sp_23_2.0)
## 2.1 - BOX PLOTS RICHNESS ----
Dataset_spp_richness_post_2023 <- read_xlsx("C:/Users/Leonardo/Desktop/2308 Quality
assurance training/02_R Project/2308 Quality assurance
training/Data/Dataset_spp_richness_post_2023.xlsx")
## Box plot Species richness for each team for 2023 POST-TRAINING
box_plot_rich_23_post <- Dataset_spp_richness_post_2023 |>
  ggplot(aes(x = team, y = spp_richness, fill = team)) +
  stat_boxplot(geom = "errorbar") +
  geom_boxplot() +
  theme_bw() +
  theme(legend.position = "none") +
  ylab("Species richness") +
  ggtitle("Species richness box plot for 2023")

ggsave("Box_plot_spp_rich_2023_post.jpeg", box_plot_rich_23_post,
  width = 180,
  height = 180,
  units = "mm")
## kruskal-wallis & Pairwise Wilcoxon Rank Sum Test
kruskal.test(spp_richness~team, data = Dataset_spp_richness_post_2023)

pairwise.wilcox.test(Dataset_spp_richness_post_2023$spp_richness,
  Dataset_spp_richness_post_2023$team, p.adjust.method = "none")
## Box plot Species richness for each plot for 2023 POST-TRAINING
box_plot_rich_23_post_plot <- Dataset_spp_richness_post_2023 |>
  ggplot(aes(x = plot, y = spp_richness, fill = plot)) +
  stat_boxplot(geom = "errorbar") +
  geom_boxplot() +
  theme_bw() +
  theme(legend.position = "none") +
  ylab("Species richness") +
  ggtitle("Species richness box plot per plot for 2023 (post-training)")

ggsave("Box_plot_spp_rich_2023_post_plot.jpeg", box_plot_rich_23_post_plot,
  width = 180,
  height = 180,
  units = "mm")
## kruskal-wallis & Pairwise Wilcoxon Rank Sum Test
kruskal.test(spp_richness~plot, data = Dataset_spp_richness_post_2023)

pairwise.wilcox.test(Dataset_spp_richness_post_2023$spp_richness,
  Dataset_spp_richness_post_2023$plot, p.adjust.method = "none")

```

```

## PRE- AND POST-TRAINING TOGETHER (2023) ----
## Species richness between pre- and post- for plots ----
box_plot_rich_16_23_plot <- data_pre_post_2023 %>%
  ggplot(aes(x = plot, y = spp_richness, fill = event))+
  stat_boxplot(geom = "errorbar")+
  geom_boxplot()+
  theme_bw()+
  ylab("SPECIES RICHNESS")+
  xlab("PLOTS")+
  theme(axis.text.x=element_text(size=15))+
  theme(axis.text.y=element_text(size=15))+
  theme(legend.text = element_text(size = 15))+
  stat_compare_means(method = "wilcox.test", label.y = 40, size = 5)

```

```

ggsave("box_plot_rich_23_pre&post.jpeg", box_plot_rich_16_23_plot,
  width = 280,
  height = 260,
  unit = "mm")

```

```

## Species richness between pre- and post- for teams ----
box_plot_rich_16_23_team <- data_pre_post_2023 %>%
  ggplot(aes(x = team, y = spp_richness, fill = event))+
  stat_boxplot(geom = "errorbar")+
  geom_boxplot()+
  theme_bw()+
  ylab("SPECIES RICHNESS")+
  xlab("TEAM") +
  theme(axis.text.x=element_text(size=15))+
  theme(axis.text.y=element_text(size=15))+
  theme(legend.text = element_text(size = 15))+
  stat_compare_means(method = "wilcox.test", label.y = 40, size = 5)

```

```

ggsave("box_plot_rich_16_23_team_PRE&POST.jpeg", box_plot_rich_16_23_team,
  width = 280,
  height = 260,
  unit = "mm")

```

Script 03 - Vegetation layer percentage cover analysis, box plots elaboration and Kruskal-Wallis test for the pre-training and post-training in 2023 and the post-training in 2016

```

## SCRIPT 03 - ANALYSIS OF VEGETATION LAYERS COVER ----

```

```

library(tidyverse)
library(ggpubr)

```

```

## 2016: POST-TRAINING ----
# 01-BOX PLOTS OF COVER ----
## total cover per team
box_plot_tot_cov_16 <- data_lc_16 |>
  select(team, plot, total_cov) |>

```

```

ggplot(aes(x = team, y = total_cov, fill = team))+
stat_boxplot(geom = "errorbar") +
geom_boxplot() +
theme_bw() +
theme(legend.position = "none") +
ylab("OVERALL % COVER") +
xlab("TEAM")+
ggtitle("Overall cover for 2016")

ggsave("Box_plot_2016_Tot_cov.jpeg", box_plot_tot_cov_16,
width = 200,
height = 200,
units = "mm")
## kruskal-wallis & Pairwise Wilcoxon Rank Sum Test
kruskal.test(total_cov~team, data = data_lc_16)

pairwise.wilcox.test(data_lc_16$total_cov, data_lc_16$team, p.adjust.method = "none")
## total cover per plot
box_plot_tot_cov_16_plot <- data_lc_16 |>
select(team, plot, total_cov) |>
ggplot(aes(x = plot, y = total_cov, fill = plot))+
stat_boxplot(geom = "errorbar") +
geom_boxplot() +
theme_bw() +
theme(legend.position = "none") +
ylab("OVERALL % COVER") +
xlab("PLOTS")+
ggtitle("Overall cover for 2016")

ggsave("Box_plot_2016_Tot_cov_plot.jpeg", box_plot_tot_cov_16_plot,
width = 200,
height = 200,
units = "mm")
## kruskal-wallis & Pairwise Wilcoxon Rank Sum Test
kruskal.test(total_cov~plot, data = data_lc_16)

pairwise.wilcox.test(data_lc_16$total_cov, data_lc_16$plot, p.adjust.method = "none")
## tree layer cover per team
Tree_cov_16 <- data_lc_16 |>
select(team, plot, tree_cov) |>
ggplot(aes(x = team, y = tree_cov, fill = team))+
stat_boxplot(geom = "errorbar") +
geom_boxplot() +
theme_bw() +
theme(legend.position = "none") +
ylab("TREE LAYER % COVER") +
xlab("TEAM")+
ggtitle("Tree layer cover for 2016")

```

```

ggsave("Box_plot_2016_Tree_cov.jpeg", Tree_cov_16,
       width = 200,
       height = 200,
       units = "mm")
## kruskal-wallis & Pairwise Wilcoxon Rank Sum Test
kruskal.test(tree_cov~team, data = data_lc_16)

pairwise.wilcox.test(data_lc_16$tree_cov, data_lc_16$team, p.adjust.method = "none")
## tree layer cover per plot
Tree_cov_16_plot <- data_lc_16 |>
  select(team, plot, tree_cov) |>
  ggplot(aes(x = plot, y = tree_cov, fill = plot))+
  stat_boxplot(geom = "errorbar") +
  geom_boxplot() +
  theme_bw() +
  theme(legend.position = "none") +
  ylab("TREE LAYER % COVER") +
  xlab("PLOTS")+
  ggtitle("Tree layer cover for 2016")

ggsave("Box_plot_2016_Tree_cov_plot.jpeg", Tree_cov_16_plot,
       width = 200,
       height = 200,
       units = "mm")
## kruskal-wallis & Pairwise Wilcoxon Rank Sum Test
kruskal.test(tree_cov~plot, data = data_lc_16)

pairwise.wilcox.test(data_lc_16$tree_cov, data_lc_16$plot, p.adjust.method = "none")
## shrub layer cover per team
Shrub_cov_16 <- data_lc_16 |>
  select(team, plot, shrub_cov) |>
  ggplot(aes(x = team, y = shrub_cov, fill = team))+
  stat_boxplot(geom = "errorbar") +
  geom_boxplot() +
  theme_bw() +
  theme(legend.position = "none") +
  ylab("SHRUB LAYER % COVER") +
  xlab("TEAM")+
  ggtitle("Shrub layer cover for 2016")

ggsave("Box_plot_2016_Shrub_cov.jpeg", Shrub_cov_16,
       width = 200,
       height = 200,
       units = "mm")
## kruskal-wallis & Pairwise Wilcoxon Rank Sum Test
kruskal.test(shrub_cov~team, data = data_lc_16)

pairwise.wilcox.test(data_lc_16$shrub_cov, data_lc_16$team, p.adjust.method = "none")
## shrub layer cover per plot

```

```

Shrub_cov_16_plot <- data_lc_16 |>
  select(team, plot, shrub_cov) |>
  ggplot(aes(x = plot, y = shrub_cov, fill = plot))+
  stat_boxplot(geom = "errorbar") +
  geom_boxplot() +
  theme_bw() +
  theme(legend.position = "none") +
  ylab("SHRUB LAYER % COVER") +
  xlab("PLOTS")+
  ggtitle("Shrub layer cover box plot per plot for 2016")

ggsave("Box_plot_2016_Shrub_cov_plot.jpeg", Shrub_cov_16_plot,
  width = 200,
  height = 200,
  units = "mm")
## kruskal-wallis & Pairwise Wilcoxon Rank Sum Test
kruskal.test(shrub_cov~plot, data = data_lc_16)
pairwise.wilcox.test(data_lc_16$shrub_cov, data_lc_16$plot, p.adjust.method = "none")
## herbaceous layer cover per team
herb_cov_16 <- data_lc_16 |>
  select(team, plot, herb_cov) |>
  ggplot(aes(x = team, y = herb_cov, fill = team))+
  stat_boxplot(geom = "errorbar") +
  geom_boxplot() +
  theme_bw() +
  theme(legend.position = "none") +
  ylab("HERB LAYER % COVER") +
  xlab("TEAM")+
  ggtitle("Herbaceous layer cover for 2016")

ggsave("Box_plot_2016_Herb_cov.jpeg", herb_cov_16,
  width = 200,
  height = 200,
  units = "mm")
## kruskal-wallis & Pairwise Wilcoxon Rank Sum Test
kruskal.test(herb_cov~team, data = data_lc_16)

pairwise.wilcox.test(data_lc_16$herb_cov, data_lc_16$team, p.adjust.method = "none")
## herbaceous layer cover per plot
herb_cov_16_plot <- data_lc_16 |>
  select(team, plot, herb_cov) |>
  ggplot(aes(x = plot, y = herb_cov, fill = plot))+
  stat_boxplot(geom = "errorbar") +
  geom_boxplot() +
  theme_bw() +
  theme(legend.position = "none") +
  ylab("HERB LAYER % COVER") +
  xlab("PLOTS")+
  ggtitle("Herbaceous layer cover for 2016")

```

```

ggsave("Box_plot_2016_Herb_cov_plot.jpeg", herb_cov_16_plot,
       width = 200,
       height = 200,
       units = "mm")
## kruskal-wallis & Pairwise Wilcoxon Rank Sum Test
kruskal.test(herb_cov~plot, data = data_lc_16)

pairwise.wilcox.test(data_lc_16$herb_cov, data_lc_16$plot, p.adjust.method = "none")
## litter cover per team
litter_cov_16 <- data_lc_16 |>
  select(team, plot, litter) |>
  ggplot(aes(x = team, y = litter, fill = team))+
  stat_boxplot(geom = "errorbar") +
  geom_boxplot() +
  theme_bw() +
  theme(legend.position = "none") +
  ylab("LITTER % COVER") +
  xlab("TEAM")+
  ggtitle("Litter cover for 2016")

ggsave("Box_plot_2016_litter_cover.jpeg", litter_cov_16,
       width = 200,
       height = 200,
       units = "mm")
## kruskal-wallis & Pairwise Wilcoxon Rank Sum Test
kruskal.test(litter~team, data = data_lc_16)

pairwise.wilcox.test(data_lc_16$litter, data_lc_16$team, p.adjust.method = "none")
## litter cover per plot
litter_cov_16_plot <- data_lc_16 |>
  select(team, plot, litter) |>
  ggplot(aes(x = plot, y = litter, fill = plot))+
  stat_boxplot(geom = "errorbar") +
  geom_boxplot() +
  theme_bw() +
  theme(legend.position = "none") +
  ylab("LITTER % COVER") +
  xlab("PLOTS")+
  ggtitle("Litter cover for 2016")

ggsave("Box_plot_2016_litter_cover_plot.jpeg", litter_cov_16_plot,
       width = 200,
       height = 200,
       units = "mm")
## kruskal-wallis & Pairwise Wilcoxon Rank Sum Test
kruskal.test(litter~plot, data = data_lc_16)

pairwise.wilcox.test(data_lc_16$litter, data_lc_16$plot, p.adjust.method = "none")

```

```

##* 2023: PRE-TRAINING ----
# 01-BOX PLOTS OF COVER ----
## total cover per team
box_plot_tot_cov_23_pre <- data_lc_23_pre |>
  select(team, plot, total_cov) |>
  ggplot(aes(x = team, y = total_cov, fill = team))+
  stat_boxplot(geom = "errorbar") +
  geom_boxplot() +
  theme_bw() +
  theme(legend.position = "none") +
  ylab("OVERALL % COVER") +
  xlab("TEAM")+
  ggtitle("Overall cover box plot for 2023 (Pre-training)")

ggsave("Box_plot_2023_Tot_cov_pre.jpeg", box_plot_tot_cov_23_pre,
  width = 200,
  height = 200,
  units = "mm")
## kruskal-wallis & Pairwise Wilcoxon Rank Sum Test
kruskal.test(total_cov~team, data = data_lc_23_pre)

pairwise.wilcox.test(data_lc_23_pre$total_cov, data_lc_23_pre$team, p.adjust.method =
"none")
## total cover per plot
box_plot_tot_cov_23_pre_plot <- data_lc_23_pre |>
  select(team, plot, total_cov) |>
  ggplot(aes(x = plot, y = total_cov, fill = plot))+
  stat_boxplot(geom = "errorbar") +
  geom_boxplot() +
  theme_bw() +
  theme(legend.position = "none") +
  ylab("OVERALL % COVER") +
  xlab("PLOT")+
  ggtitle("Overall cover box plot per plot for 2023 (Pre-training)")

ggsave("Box_plot_2023_Tot_cov_pre_plot.jpeg", box_plot_tot_cov_23_pre_plot,
  width = 200,
  height = 200,
  units = "mm")
## kruskal-wallis & Pairwise Wilcoxon Rank Sum Test
## kruskal-wallis test
kruskal.test(total_cov~plot, data = data_lc_23_pre)

pairwise.wilcox.test(data_lc_23_pre$total_cov, data_lc_23_pre$plot, p.adjust.method =
"none")
## Species richness between pre- and post- for teams ----
Tree_cov_23_pre <- data_lc_23_pre |>
  select(team, plot, tree_cov) |>

```

```

ggplot(aes(x = team, y = tree_cov, fill = team))+
stat_boxplot(geom = "errorbar") +
geom_boxplot() +
theme_bw() +
theme(legend.position = "none") +
ylab("TREE LAYER % COVER") +
xlab("TEAM")+
ggtitle("Tree layer cover box plot for 2023 (pre-training)")

ggsave("Box_plot_2023_Tree_cov_pre.jpeg", Tree_cov_23_pre,
width = 200,
height = 200,
units = "mm")
## kruskal-wallis & Pairwise Wilcoxon Rank Sum Test
kruskal.test(tree_cov~team, data = data_lc_23_pre)

pairwise.wilcox.test(data_lc_23_pre$tree_cov, data_lc_23_pre$team, p.adjust.method =
"none")
## tree layer cover per plot
Tree_cov_23_pre_plot <- data_lc_23_pre |>
select(team, plot, tree_cov) |>
ggplot(aes(x = plot, y = tree_cov, fill = plot))+
stat_boxplot(geom = "errorbar") +
geom_boxplot() +
theme_bw() +
theme(legend.position = "none") +
ylab("TREE LAYER % COVER") +
xlab("PLOT")+
ggtitle("Tree layer cover box plot per plot for 2023 (pre-training)")

ggsave("Box_plot_2023_Tree_cov_pre_plot.jpeg", Tree_cov_23_pre_plot,
width = 200,
height = 200,
units = "mm")
## kruskal-wallis & Pairwise Wilcoxon Rank Sum Test
kruskal.test(tree_cov~plot, data = data_lc_23_pre)

pairwise.wilcox.test(data_lc_23_pre$tree_cov, data_lc_23_pre$plot, p.adjust.method =
"none")
## shrub layer cover per team
Shrub_cov_23_pre <- data_lc_23_pre |>
select(team, plot, shrub_cov) |>
ggplot(aes(x = team, y = shrub_cov, fill = team))+
stat_boxplot(geom = "errorbar") +
geom_boxplot() +
theme_bw() +
theme(legend.position = "none") +
ylab("SHRUB LAYER % COVER") +
xlab("TEAM")+

```

```

ggtitle("Shrub layer cover box plot for 2023 (pre-training)")

ggsave("Box_plot_2023_Shrub_cov_pre.jpeg", Shrub_cov_23_pre,
       width = 200,
       height = 200,
       units = "mm")
## kruskal-wallis & Pairwise Wilcoxon Rank Sum Test
kruskal.test(shrub_cov~team, data = data_lc_23_pre)
pairwise.wilcox.test(data_lc_23_pre$shrub_cov, data_lc_23_pre$team, p.adjust.method =
"none")
## shrub layer cover per plot
Shrub_cov_23_pre_plot <- data_lc_23_pre |>
  select(team, plot, shrub_cov) |>
  ggplot(aes(x = plot, y = shrub_cov, fill = plot))+
  stat_boxplot(geom = "errorbar") +
  geom_boxplot() +
  theme_bw() +
  theme(legend.position = "none") +
  ylab("SHRUB LAYER % COVER") +
  xlab("PLOT")+
  ggtitle("Shrub layer cover box plot per plot for 2023 (pre-training)")

ggsave("Box_plot_2023_Shrub_cov_pre_plot.jpeg", Shrub_cov_23_pre_plot,
       width = 200,
       height = 200,
       units = "mm")
## kruskal-wallis & Pairwise Wilcoxon Rank Sum Test
kruskal.test(shrub_cov~plot, data = data_lc_23_pre)

pairwise.wilcox.test(data_lc_23_pre$shrub_cov, data_lc_23_pre$plot, p.adjust.method =
"none")
## herbaceous layer cover per team
herb_cov_23_pre <- data_lc_23_pre |>
  select(team, plot, herb_cov) |>
  ggplot(aes(x = team, y = herb_cov, fill = team))+
  stat_boxplot(geom = "errorbar") +
  geom_boxplot() +
  theme_bw() +
  theme(legend.position = "none") +
  ylab("HERB LAYER % COVER") +
  xlab("TEAM")+
  ggtitle("Herbaceous layer cover box plot for 2023 (pre-training)")

ggsave("Box_plot_2023_Herb_cov_pre.jpeg", herb_cov_23_pre,
       width = 200,
       height = 200,
       units = "mm")
## kruskal-wallis & Pairwise Wilcoxon Rank Sum Test
kruskal.test(herb_cov~team, data = data_lc_23_pre)

```

```

pairwise.wilcox.test(data_lc_23_pre$herb_cov, data_lc_23_pre$team, p.adjust.method =
"none")
## herbaceous layer cover per plot
herb_cov_23_pre_plot <- data_lc_23_pre |>
  select(team, plot, herb_cov) |>
  ggplot(aes(x = plot, y = herb_cov, fill = plot))+
  stat_boxplot(geom = "errorbar") +
  geom_boxplot() +
  theme_bw() +
  theme(legend.position = "none") +
  ylab("HERB LAYER % COVER") +
  xlab("PLOT")+
  ggtitle("Herbaceous layer cover box plot per plot for 2023 (pre-training)")

ggsave("Box_plot_2023_Herb_cov_pre_plot.jpeg", herb_cov_23_pre_plot,
  width = 200,
  height = 200,
  units = "mm")
## kruskal-wallis & Pairwise Wilcoxon Rank Sum Test
kruskal.test(herb_cov~plot, data = data_lc_23_pre)

pairwise.wilcox.test(data_lc_23_pre$herb_cov, data_lc_23_pre$plot, p.adjust.method =
"none")
## litter cover per team
litter_cov_23_pre <- data_lc_23_pre |>
  select(team, plot, litter) |>
  ggplot(aes(x = team, y = litter, fill = team))+
  stat_boxplot(geom = "errorbar") +
  geom_boxplot() +
  theme_bw() +
  theme(legend.position = "none") +
  ylab("LITTER % COVER") +
  xlab("TEAM")+
  ggtitle("Litter cover box plot for 2023 (pre-training)")

ggsave("Box_plot_2023_litter_cover_pre.jpeg", litter_cov_23_pre,
  width = 200,
  height = 200,
  units = "mm")
## kruskal-wallis & Pairwise Wilcoxon Rank Sum Test
kruskal.test(litter~team, data = data_lc_23_pre)

pairwise.wilcox.test(data_lc_23_pre$litter, data_lc_23_pre$team, p.adjust.method = "none")
## litter cover per plot
litter_cov_23_pre_plot <- data_lc_23_pre |>
  select(team, plot, litter) |>
  ggplot(aes(x = plot, y = litter, fill = plot))+
  stat_boxplot(geom = "errorbar") +

```

```

geom_boxplot() +
theme_bw() +
theme(legend.position = "none") +
ylab("LITTER % COVER") +
xlab("PLOT")+
ggtitle("Litter cover box plot per plot for 2023 (pre-training)")

ggsave("Box_plot_2023_litter_cover_pre_plot.jpeg", litter_cov_23_pre_plot,
width = 200,
height = 200,
units = "mm")
## kruskal-wallis & Pairwise Wilcoxon Rank Sum Test
kruskal.test(litter~plot, data = data_lc_23_pre)

pairwise.wilcox.test(data_lc_23_pre$litter, data_lc_23_pre$plot, p.adjust.method = "none")

#* 2023: POST-TRAINING ----
# 01-BOX PLOTS OF COVER ----
## total cover per team
box_plot_tot_cov_23_post <- data_lc_23_post |>
select(team, plot, total_cov) |>
ggplot(aes(x = team, y = total_cov, fill = team))+
stat_boxplot(geom = "errorbar") +
geom_boxplot() +
theme_bw() +
theme(legend.position = "none") +
ylab("OVERALL % COVER") +
xlab("TEAM")+
ggtitle("Overall cover box plot for 2023 (Post-training)")

ggsave("Box_plot_2023_Tot_cov_post.jpeg", box_plot_tot_cov_23_post,
width = 200,
height = 200,
units = "mm")
## kruskal-wallis & Pairwise Wilcoxon Rank Sum Test
kruskal.test(total_cov~team, data = data_lc_23_post)

pairwise.wilcox.test(data_lc_23_post$total_cov, data_lc_23_post$team, p.adjust.method =
"none")
## total cover per plot
box_plot_tot_cov_23_post_plot <- data_lc_23_post |>
select(team, plot, total_cov) |>
ggplot(aes(x = plot, y = total_cov, fill = plot))+
stat_boxplot(geom = "errorbar") +
geom_boxplot() +
theme_bw() +
theme(legend.position = "none") +
ylab("OVERALL % COVER") +
xlab("PLOT")+

```

```

ggtitle("Overall cover box plot per plot for 2023 (Post-training)")

ggsave("Box_plot_2023_Tot_cov_post_plot.jpeg", box_plot_tot_cov_23_post_plot,
       width = 200,
       height = 200,
       units = "mm")
## kruskal-wallis & Pairwise Wilcoxon Rank Sum Test
kruskal.test(total_cov~plot, data = data_lc_23_post)

pairwise.wilcox.test(data_lc_23_post$total_cov, data_lc_23_post$plot, p.adjust.method =
"none")
## tree layer cover per team
Tree_cov_23_post <- data_lc_23_post |>
  select(team, plot, tree_cov) |>
  ggplot(aes(x = team, y = tree_cov, fill = team))+
  stat_boxplot(geom = "errorbar") +
  geom_boxplot() +
  theme_bw() +
  theme(legend.position = "none") +
  ylab("TREE LAYER % COVER") +
  xlab("TEAM")+
  ggtitle("Tree layer cover box plot for 2023 (post-training)")

ggsave("Box_plot_2023_Tree_cov_post.jpeg", Tree_cov_23_post,
       width = 200,
       height = 200,
       units = "mm")
## kruskal-wallis & Pairwise Wilcoxon Rank Sum Test
kruskal.test(tree_cov~team, data = data_lc_23_post)

pairwise.wilcox.test(data_lc_23_post$tree_cov, data_lc_23_post$team, p.adjust.method =
"none")
## tree layer cover per plot
Tree_cov_23_post_plot <- data_lc_23_post |>
  select(team, plot, tree_cov) |>
  ggplot(aes(x = plot, y = tree_cov, fill = plot))+
  stat_boxplot(geom = "errorbar") +
  geom_boxplot() +
  theme_bw() +
  theme(legend.position = "none") +
  ylab("TREE LAYER % COVER") +
  xlab("PLOT")+
  ggtitle("Tree layer cover box plot per plot for 2023 (post-training)")

ggsave("Box_plot_2023_Tree_cov_post_plot.jpeg", Tree_cov_23_post_plot,
       width = 200,
       height = 200,
       units = "mm")
## kruskal-wallis & Pairwise Wilcoxon Rank Sum Test

```

```

kruskal.test(tree_cov~plot, data = data_lc_23_post)
pairwise.wilcox.test(data_lc_23_post$tree_cov, data_lc_23_post$plot, p.adjust.method =
"none")
## shrub layer cover per team
Shrub_cov_23_post <- data_lc_23_post |>
  select(team, plot, shrub_cov) |>
  ggplot(aes(x = team, y = shrub_cov, fill = team))+
  stat_boxplot(geom = "errorbar") +
  geom_boxplot() +
  theme_bw() +
  theme(legend.position = "none") +
  ylab("SHRUB LAYER % COVER") +
  xlab("TEAM")+
  ggtitle("Shrub layer cover box plot for 2023 (post-training)")

ggsave("Box_plot_2023_Shrub_cov_post.jpeg", Shrub_cov_23_post,
  width = 200,
  height = 200,
  units = "mm")
## kruskal-wallis & Pairwise Wilcoxon Rank Sum Test
kruskal.test(shrub_cov~team, data = data_lc_23_post)

pairwise.wilcox.test(data_lc_23_post$shrub_cov, data_lc_23_post$team, p.adjust.method =
"none")
## shrub layer cover per plot
Shrub_cov_23_post_plot <- data_lc_23_post |>
  select(team, plot, shrub_cov) |>
  ggplot(aes(x = plot, y = shrub_cov, fill = plot))+
  stat_boxplot(geom = "errorbar") +
  geom_boxplot() +
  theme_bw() +
  theme(legend.position = "none") +
  ylab("SHRUB LAYER % COVER") +
  xlab("PLOT")+
  ggtitle("Shrub layer cover box plot per plot for 2023 (post-training)")

ggsave("Box_plot_2023_Shrub_cov_post_plot.jpeg", Shrub_cov_23_post_plot,
  width = 200,
  height = 200,
  units = "mm")
## kruskal-wallis & Pairwise Wilcoxon Rank Sum Test
kruskal.test(shrub_cov~plot, data = data_lc_23_post)

pairwise.wilcox.test(data_lc_23_post$shrub_cov, data_lc_23_post$plot, p.adjust.method =
"none")
## herbaceous layer cover per team
herb_cov_23_post <- data_lc_23_post |>
  select(team, plot, herb_cov) |>
  ggplot(aes(x = team, y = herb_cov, fill = team))+

```

```

stat_boxplot(geom = "errorbar") +
geom_boxplot() +
theme_bw() +
theme(legend.position = "none") +
ylab("HERB LAYER % COVER") +
xlab("TEAM")+
ggtitle("Herbaceous layer cover box plot for 2023 (post-training)")

ggsave("Box_plot_2023_Herb_cov_post.jpeg", herb_cov_23_post,
width = 200,
height = 200,
units = "mm")
## kruskal-wallis & Pairwise Wilcoxon Rank Sum Test
kruskal.test(herb_cov~team, data = data_lc_23_post)

pairwise.wilcox.test(data_lc_23_post$herb_cov, data_lc_23_post$team, p.adjust.method =
"none")
## herbaceous layer cover per plot
herb_cov_23_post_plot <- data_lc_23_post |>
select(team, plot, herb_cov) |>
ggplot(aes(x = plot, y = herb_cov, fill = plot))+
stat_boxplot(geom = "errorbar") +
geom_boxplot() +
theme_bw() +
theme(legend.position = "none") +
ylab("HERB LAYER % COVER") +
xlab("PLOT")+
ggtitle("Herbaceous layer cover box plot per plotfor 2023 (post-training)")

ggsave("Box_plot_2023_Herb_cov_post_plot.jpeg", herb_cov_23_post_plot,
width = 200,
height = 200,
units = "mm")
## kruskal-wallis & Pairwise Wilcoxon Rank Sum Test
kruskal.test(herb_cov~plot, data = data_lc_23_post)

pairwise.wilcox.test(data_lc_23_post$herb_cov, data_lc_23_post$plot, p.adjust.method =
"none")
## litter cover per team
litter_cov_23_post <- data_lc_23_post |>
select(team, plot, litter) |>
ggplot(aes(x = team, y = litter, fill = team))+
stat_boxplot(geom = "errorbar") +
geom_boxplot() +
theme_bw() +
theme(legend.position = "none") +
ylab("LITTER % COVER") +
xlab("TEAM")+
ggtitle("Litter cover box plot for 2023 (post-training)")

```

```

ggsave("Box_plot_2023_litter_cover_post.jpeg", litter_cov_23_post,
       width = 200,
       height = 200,
       units = "mm")
## kruskal-wallis & Pairwise Wilcoxon Rank Sum Test
kruskal.test(litter~team, data = data_lc_23_post)

pairwise.wilcox.test(data_lc_23_post$litter, data_lc_23_post$team, p.adjust.method =
"none")
## litter cover per plot
litter_cov_23_post_plot <- data_lc_23_post |>
  select(team, plot, litter) |>
  ggplot(aes(x = plot, y = litter, fill = plot))+
  stat_boxplot(geom = "errorbar") +
  geom_boxplot() +
  theme_bw() +
  theme(legend.position = "none") +
  ylab("LITTER % COVER") +
  xlab("PLOT")+
  ggtitle("Litter cover box plot per plot for 2023 (post-training)")

ggsave("Box_plot_2023_litter_cover_post_plot.jpeg", litter_cov_23_post_plot,
       width = 200,
       height = 200,
       units = "mm")
## kruskal-wallis & Pairwise Wilcoxon Rank Sum Test
kruskal.test(litter~plot, data = data_lc_23_post)

pairwise.wilcox.test(data_lc_23_post$litter, data_lc_23_post$plot, p.adjust.method = "none")

##* PRE- AND POST-TRAINING TOGETHER (2023) ----
### PLOT BY PLOT - - - -
## Overall cover per plot
pre_post_tot_plot <- data_lc_23 %>%
  ggplot(aes(x = plot, y = total_cov, fill = event))+
  stat_boxplot(geom = "errorbar")+
  geom_boxplot()+
  theme_bw()+
  ylab("OVERALL COVER") +
  xlab("PLOTS")+
  xlab("PLOTS")+
  theme(axis.text.x=element_text(size=15))+
  theme(axis.text.y=element_text(size=15))+
  theme(legend.text = element_text(size = 15))+
  stat_compare_means(method = "wilcox.test", label.y = 100, size = 5)

ggsave("PRE_POST_2023_Tot_cov_plot.jpeg", pre_post_tot_plot,
       width = 280,

```

```

    height = 260,
    units = "mm")
## Tree cover per plot
pre_post_tree_plot <- data_lc_23 %>%
  ggplot(aes(x = plot, y = tree_cov, fill = event))+
  stat_boxplot(geom = "errorbar")+
  geom_boxplot()+
  theme_bw()+
  ylab("TREE COVER") +
  xlab("PLOTS")+
  theme(axis.text.x=element_text(size=15))+
  theme(axis.text.y=element_text(size=15))+
  theme(legend.text = element_text(size = 15))+
  stat_compare_means(method = "wilcox.test", label.y = 100, size = 5)

ggsave("PRE_POST_2023_tree_plot.jpeg", pre_post_tree_plot,
  width = 280,
  height = 260,
  units = "mm")
## Shrub cover per plot
pre_post_shrub_plot <- data_lc_23 %>%
  ggplot(aes(x = plot, y = shrub_cov, fill = event))+
  stat_boxplot(geom = "errorbar")+
  geom_boxplot()+
  theme_bw()+
  ylab("SHRUB COVER") +
  xlab("PLOTS")+
  theme(axis.text.x=element_text(size=15))+
  theme(axis.text.y=element_text(size=15))+
  theme(legend.text = element_text(size = 15))+
  stat_compare_means(method = "wilcox.test", label.y = 75, size = 5)

ggsave("PRE_POST_2023_shrub_plot.jpeg", pre_post_shrub_plot,
  width = 280,
  height = 260,
  units = "mm")
## Herbaceous cover per plot
pre_post_herb_plot <- data_lc_23 %>%
  ggplot(aes(x = plot, y = herb_cov, fill = event))+
  stat_boxplot(geom = "errorbar")+
  geom_boxplot()+
  theme_bw()+
  ylab("HERB COVER") +
  xlab("PLOTS")+
  theme(axis.text.x=element_text(size=15))+
  theme(axis.text.y=element_text(size=15))+
  theme(legend.text = element_text(size = 15))+
  stat_compare_means(method = "wilcox.test", label.y = 75, size = 5)

```

```

ggsave("PRE_POST_2023_herb_plot.jpeg", pre_post_herb_plot,
       width = 280,
       height = 260,
       units = "mm")
## Litter cover per plot
pre_post_litter_plot <- data_lc_23 %>%
  ggplot(aes(x = plot, y = litter, fill = event))+
  stat_boxplot(geom = "errorbar")+
  geom_boxplot()+
  theme_bw()+
  ylab("LITTER COVER") +
  xlab("PLOTS")+
  theme(axis.text.x=element_text(size=15))+
  theme(axis.text.y=element_text(size=15))+
  theme(legend.text = element_text(size = 15))+
  stat_compare_means(method = "wilcox.test", label.y = 100, size = 5)

```

```

ggsave("PRE_POST_2023_litter_plot.jpeg", pre_post_litter_plot,
       width = 280,
       height = 260,
       units = "mm")

```

TEAM BY TEAM - - - -

Overall cover per team

```

pre_post_tot_team <- data_lc_23 %>%
  ggplot(aes(x = team, y = total_cov, fill = event))+
  stat_boxplot(geom = "errorbar")+
  geom_boxplot()+
  theme_bw()+
  ylab("OVERALL COVER") +
  xlab("TEAMS")+
  theme(axis.text.x=element_text(size=15))+
  theme(axis.text.y=element_text(size=15))+
  theme(legend.text = element_text(size = 15))+
  stat_compare_means(method = "wilcox.test", label.y = 100, size = 5)

```

```

ggsave("PRE_POST_2023_Tot_cov_team.jpeg", pre_post_tot_team,
       width = 280,
       height = 260,
       units = "mm")

```

Tree cover per team

```

pre_post_tree_team <- data_lc_23 %>%
  ggplot(aes(x = team, y = tree_cov, fill = event))+
  stat_boxplot(geom = "errorbar")+
  geom_boxplot()+
  theme_bw()+
  ylab("TREE COVER") +
  xlab("TEAMS")+
  theme(axis.text.x=element_text(size=15))+

```

```

theme(axis.text.y=element_text(size=15))+
theme(legend.text = element_text(size = 15))+
stat_compare_means(method = "wilcox.test", label.y = 100, size = 5)

ggsave("PRE_POST_2023_tree_cov_team.jpeg", pre_post_tree_team,
       width = 280,
       height = 260,
       units = "mm")
## Shrub cover per team
pre_post_shrub_team <- data_lc_23 %>%
  ggplot(aes(x = team, y = shrub_cov, fill = event))+
  stat_boxplot(geom = "errorbar")+
  geom_boxplot()+
  theme_bw()+
  ylab("SHRUB COVER") +
  xlab("TEAMS")+
  theme(axis.text.x=element_text(size=15))+
  theme(axis.text.y=element_text(size=15))+
  theme(legend.text = element_text(size = 15))+
  stat_compare_means(method = "wilcox.test", label.y = 75, size = 5)

ggsave("PRE_POST_2023_shrub_cov_team.jpeg", pre_post_shrub_team,
       width = 280,
       height = 260,
       units = "mm")
## Herbaceous cover per team
pre_post_herb_team <- data_lc_23 %>%
  ggplot(aes(x = team, y = herb_cov, fill = event))+
  stat_boxplot(geom = "errorbar")+
  geom_boxplot()+
  theme_bw()+
  ylab("HERB COVER") +
  xlab("TEAMS")+
  theme(axis.text.x=element_text(size=15))+
  theme(axis.text.y=element_text(size=15))+
  theme(legend.text = element_text(size = 15))+
  stat_compare_means(method = "wilcox.test", label.y = 80, size = 5)

ggsave("PRE_POST_2023_herb_cov_team.jpeg", pre_post_herb_team,
       width = 280,
       height = 260,
       units = "mm")
## Litter cover per team
pre_post_litter_team <- data_lc_23 %>%
  ggplot(aes(x = team, y = litter, fill = event))+
  stat_boxplot(geom = "errorbar")+
  geom_boxplot()+
  theme_bw()+
  ylab("LITTER COVER") +

```

```
xlab("TEAMS")+
theme(axis.text.x=element_text(size=15))+
theme(axis.text.y=element_text(size=15))+
theme(legend.text = element_text(size = 15))+
stat_compare_means(method = "wilcox.test", label.y = 100, size = 5)
```

```
ggsave("PRE_POST_2023_litter_cov_team.jpeg", pre_post_litter_team,
width = 280,
height = 260,
units = "mm")
```

Script 05 - determination of species richness for 2011 and 2012 and calculation of the percentage coefficient of variation for each T & I course

SCRIP 05 - ANALYSIS OF CV% YEAR BY YEAR

```
rm(list=ls())
## Loading packages
library(tidyverse)
library(readxl)
library(labdsv)
library(vegan)
## Loading data ----
cv09_data <- read_xlsx("C:/Users/Leonardo/Desktop/2308 Quality assurance training/02_R
Project/2308 Quality assurance training/Data/stagesxLeonardo/SPP_2009.xlsx")
cv11_data <- read_xlsx("C:/Users/Leonardo/Desktop/2308 Quality assurance training/02_R
Project/2308 Quality assurance training/Data/stagesxLeonardo/SPP_2011.xlsx")
cv12_data <- read_xlsx("C:/Users/Leonardo/Desktop/2308 Quality assurance training/02_R
Project/2308 Quality assurance training/Data/stagesxLeonardo/SPP_2012.xlsx")
### cv16 and cv23 loaded with scrip01_A
## naming files FOR 2016 and 2023
cv16_data <- data_sp_16
cv23_data <- data_sp_23_post
## Coefficient of variation (2009)
cv09_data %>%
  dplyr::select(team, plot, species) %>%
  unite(team_plot, c(team, plot))

m09 <- cv09_data$species %>% mean()
sd09 <- cv09_data$species %>% sd()

cv09 <- ((sd09/m09)* 100)
## Coefficient of variation (2011)
matr_11 <- cv11_data |>
  dplyr::select(team, plot, species, percentage_cover)

matr_11 <- matr_11 |>
  unite(team_plot, c(team, plot))
```

```

matr_11 <- matr_11 |> as.data.frame()

matr_11 <- matr_11 |> matlify()

specpool(matr_11)

nspp_11 <- specnumber(matr_11)

m11 <- mean(nspp_11)
sd11 <- sd(nspp_11)

cv11 <- ((sd11/m11)*100)
## Coefficient of variation (2012)
matr_12 <- cv12_data |>
  dplyr::select(team, plot, species, percentage_cover)

matr_12 <- matr_12 |>
  unite(team_plot, c(team, plot))

matr_12 <- matr_12 |> as.data.frame()

matr_12 <- matr_12 |> matlify() %>% drop_na()

specpool(matr_12)

nspp_12 <- specnumber(matr_12)

m12 <- mean(nspp_12)
sd12 <- sd(nspp_12)

cv12 <- ((sd12/m12)*100)
## Coefficient of variation (2016)
matr_16 <- cv16_data |>
  dplyr::select(team, Plot, species, percentage_cover)

matr_16 <- matr_16 |>
  unite(team_plot, c(team, Plot))

matr_16 <- matr_16 |> as.data.frame()

matr_16 <- matr_16 |> matlify()

specpool(matr_16)

nspp_16 <- specnumber(matr_16)

m16 <- mean(nspp_16)
sd16 <- sd(nspp_16)

```

```

cv16 <- ((sd16/m16)*100)
## Coefficient of variation (2023)
matr_23 <- cv23_data |>
  dplyr::select(team, Plot, species, percentage_cover)

matr_23 <- matr_23 |>
  unite(team_plot, c(team, Plot))

matr_23 <- matr_23 |> as.data.frame()

matr_23 <- matr_23 |> matrifify()

specpool(matr_23)

nspp_23 <- specnumber(matr_23)

m23 <- mean(nspp_23)
sd23 <- sd(nspp_23)

cv23 <- ((sd23/m23)*100)
## Creating a vector with each cv%
cv_vector <- c(cv09, cv11, cv12, cv16, cv23)
## Creating a data frame with the years and the cv%
cv_vector <- data.frame(cv_vector, year = c(2009, 2011, 2012, 2016, 2023))
## Generating the plot
graph_cv <- cv_vector %>%
  ggplot(aes(x= year, y= cv_vector)) +
  geom_point(size = 5,
             color = "darkgreen") +
  scale_x_continuous(limits = c(2008, 2024), breaks = c(2008, 2010, 2012, 2014, 2016, 2018,
2020, 2022, 2024)) +
  theme_bw() +
  theme(legend.position = "none") +
  ylab("CV%") +
  xlab("YEAR") +
  ggtitle("PERCENTAGE COEFFICIENT OF VARIATION FOR SPECIES RICHNESS")

ggsave("CV.jpeg", graph_cv,
       width = 200,
       height = 200,
       units = "mm")

```

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